

FLOOD-serv

D6.3 First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan

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List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
ANO	A.N.O. SISTEMAS DE INFORMATICA E SERVICOS LDA
ANSWARETECH	ANSWARETECH SL
BILBAO	AYUNTAMIENTO DE BILBAO
BSK	BRATISLAVSKY SAMOSPRAVNY KRAJ
CELLENT	CELLENT AG
CMVNF	MUNICIPIO DE VILA NOVA DE FAMALICAO
D6.1	D6.1 Community of Interest Build-up & Engagement Strategy
D6.2	D6.2 Dissemination Plan
D6.3	D6.3 First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan
D6.4	D6.4 Sustainability and Exploitation First Plan
D6.5	D6.5 Sustainability and Exploitation Final Plan
D6.6	D6.6 Final Communication and Dissemination Report
DDNI	INTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE - DEZVOLTARE DELTA DUNARI
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EXDWARF	EXDWARF CONSULTING SRO
GA	Grant Agreement
GENOVA	COMUNE DI GENOVA (<i>Municipality of Genova</i>)
GIS	Geographic Information System
GOV2U	GOVERNMENT TO YOU
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IP TULCEA	INSTITUTIA PREFECTULUI JUDETUL TULCEA
Mx	Month X
REA	Research Executive Agency
SIVECO	SIVECO S.A. ROMANIA
WPx	Work Package x

Executive summary

This deliverable under the title “*D6.3 First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan*” consists a report of the communication and dissemination activities made during the first 18 months of project’s implementation. Additionally, it presents an update of the Dissemination plan for the period M19-M36. Particularly it addresses four main aspects: a) the communication and disseminations tools (*website, press releases, newsletter issues, social media etc.*) that project partners used for promoting the project and its results, b) the communication and dissemination activities performed such as workshops and events organized by the FLOOD-serv, participation in public events (*third party events*), media coverage, publications and so on, c) the performance measurement of tools and activities and assessment of their effectiveness according the KPIs set in deliverable “D6.2 Dissemination Plan”, and d) an update of the Dissemination Plan.

D6.3 is a public deliverable of this project, part of WP6, and it contains information around the project’s scope and objectives as well as the work package. It ensures that no prior knowledge to the project, the Description of Work (*DoW*), and the other WP6 deliverables is requested. Overall, the current document is based on, and is consistent with, the DoW and the Grant Agreement, but is not a substitute for reading these documents.

1 Introduction

1.1 Overall summary of the project

FLOOD-serv is a **three year project** that was launched in August 2016 aiming to raise awareness on flood risks and enable collective risk mitigation solutions and response actions by using the collaborative power of ICT networks and citizens' involvement. It is an Innovation Action funded under the "ICT-enabled open government" topic (*INSO-1-2015*) of the Horizon 2020 programme - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Europe in a changing world - Inclusive, Innovative and Reflective Societies.

The **overall objective** of FLOOD-serv is to develop and to provide a pro-active and personalised citizen-centric public service application that will enhance the involvement of the citizen and will harness the collaborative power of ICT networks (*networks of people, of knowledge, of sensors*) to raise awareness on flood risks and to enable collective risk mitigation solutions and response actions.

The project **aims** at having a strong impact on the efficiency and overall adoption of new pro-active and personalised citizen-centric public service applications based on new web technologies and mobile technologies.

Technically the project will focus on developing a collaborative platform that will link citizen, public authorities and other stakeholders and enables the public to be warned en masse so that actions can be taken to reduce the adverse effects of the flood. The project will prepare, develop and implement test pilots, which will test, verify, demonstrate and validate the project solutions in different conditions and different areas of Europe. The 5 pilot sites are:

- **Danube Delta**, Romania
- **Genova**, Italy
- **Bilbao**, Spain
- **Bratislava Self-Governing Region**, Slovakia
- **Ave Valley Region**, Portugal

The activities foreseen in DoW for the realization of the project have been divided into 7 work packages:

<i>WP number</i>	<i>WP Title</i>
WP1	Project management and coordination
WP2	Comparative study and analysis on flood risk management public services in the selected regions
WP3	Development of FLOOD-serv system components
WP4	FLOOD-serv collaborative and personalized citizen-centric platform
WP5	Verification, Piloting, Evaluation and Validation
WP6	Stakeholders Engagement, Dissemination and Exploitation
WP7	Ethics requirements

Table 1 : List of FLOOD-serv work packages

The current document is a public deliverable of WP6 “*Stakeholders Engagement, Dissemination and Exploitation*”.

1.2 About WP6

This work package under the title “*Stakeholders Engagement, Dissemination and Exploitation*” is a subset of the FLOOD-serv project and according to the DoW, it is assigned to:

- Launch an effective internal and external communication and dissemination strategy while assisting other work packages to meet their outreach objectives.
- Establish a consistent and distinctive project identity and maintain a favorable reputation.
- Communicate and disseminate - widely and effective - the project’s objective’s, methodology, benefits and findings among wide variety of stakeholders, from public bodies who are involved in flood mitigation and response to policy-makers and academics, as well as the general public in order to maximize the project’s impact and visibility and to ensure the take-up of the pilot methodologies and tools in the long-term.
- Reach and involve target groups through systematic use of a variety of dissemination techniques and means
- Link with other projects and CSAs funded under the ICT-enabled open government call as well as other international projects and organizations of relevance for the FLOOD-serv project, integrating knowledge coming from these projects, investigating collaboration opportunities and exploiting synergies.
- Define a post-project sustainability and exploitation strategy and planning to sustain project outcomes and maximize its impact.

Within WP6 all consortium partners have an active role in participating and undertaking activities linked to its specific tasks. This work package is responsible for the deliverables listed in the table below.

<i>Deliverable number</i>	<i>Deliverable Title</i>	<i>Dissemination Level</i>
D6.1	Community of Interest Build-up & Engagement Strategy	Public
D6.2	Dissemination Plan	Public
D6.3	First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan	Public
D6.4	Sustainability and Exploitation First Plan	Confidential
D6.5	Sustainability and Exploitation Final Plan	Confidential
D6.6	Final Communication and Dissemination Report	Public

Table 2 : List of WP6 deliverables

1.3 The deliverable D6.3

1.3.1 Scope

According to the DoW, the scope of this deliverable is to provide a full report on the communication and dissemination activities made by the FLOOD-serv consortium during the first 18 months of project's implementation. Moreover, to assess the performance of the activities and present an update of the plan for ensuring the high visibility of the project.

1.3.2 Intended audience

<i>Intended audience</i>	<i>Reasons for interest in reading</i>
FLOOD-serv project partners	To be informed about the communication and dissemination activities performed within M1-M18; and the updated plan for the dissemination activities for M19-M36.
European Commission	To assess the implemented actions for the period M1-M18 and the updates on the dissemination plan for the period M19-M36.
Target groups <i>End-users, decision makers/replication actors, stakeholders, policy makers</i>	To be informed about the project in general, its scope, the dissemination activities performed within the reporting period and discover how they could be benefited and/or engaged.
Representatives of organizations involved into similar projects	To share knowledge, information, best practices and so on that could be useful in implementing their respective activities. Also this document can introduce them the FLOOD-serv project and potential synergies in the field of dissemination could be identified.
Anyone interested	To be informed about the available tools and methods for promoting in general ideas and/or results of a project. Moreover, to raise awareness on project's topic.

Table 3 : Intended audience

1.3.3 Structure

The current document is comprised of seven chapters and three appendices. The first chapter introduces to the reader the FLOOD-serv project and the WP6 and it provides information about this deliverable (D6.3) such as its scope, the intended audience etc. The second chapter describes the objectives and the audience of the communication and dissemination activities of the project. The third chapter presents the tools and channels employed and in parallel it delineates all the actions that were undertaken by using them within the period M1-M18. The fourth chapter lists the communication and dissemination activities made and highlights some of these actions.

The fifth chapter provides an assessment of the reported activities and the sixth an update of the dissemination plan. Lastly, the conclusion summarizes the main points and issues presented in this deliverable.

1.3.4 Methodology followed

The creation of this deliverable was based on the close collaboration among the consortium for reporting efficiently the performed activities in the first 18 months of the project. Throughout this period each partner informed the WP6 leader for the developments on the topic. Bi-annually, they provided to Gov2u a consolidated report with these activities for ensuring the quality of the provided information. The initial draft version of the “D6.3 First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan” deliverable was written after collecting all the reports. Later on, it was circulated via email communication to the consortium for reviewing and commenting. After incorporating all comments/suggestions, WP6 leader sent the final version to the project coordinator (*SIVECO*) for submission to REA.

1.3.5 Quality of the document

For ensuring the quality of the current document, online communication on the topic via emails and teleconferences was conducted. Gov2u, as WP6 leader, prepared the initial draft and distributed it to project partners for review and contribution. This deliverable uses the official template of the FLOOD-serv project and language quality control has been performed

1.3.6 Relation with other WP6 deliverables

This deliverable constitutes a report about the communication and dissemination activities performed the first 18 months of project’s implementation and presents the updated plan for the upcoming 18 months. For this reason it is interrelated with the rest of WP6 deliverables.

<i>WP6 Deliverables</i>	<i>Dependencies and relation</i>
<i>D6.1 Community of Interest Build-up & Engagement Strategy</i>	It has been released on Month 3 (<i>October 2016</i>). The deliverable presents the typologies of stakeholders and end users for FLOOD-serv Platform and their potential motivation to participate in the project and a detailed plan for creating a wider constituency within which the consortium will operate and produce its work. D6.3 presents activities made for Engaging stakeholders
<i>D6.2 Dissemination Plan</i>	It has been released on Month 4 (<i>November 2016</i>). The deliverable describes the dissemination strategy and the respective actions that will be implemented by the FLOOD-serv consortium during the project’s lifetime. Moreover, it defines partners’ roles and responsibilities and sets the success criteria for the evaluation of the dissemination activities foreseen in the presented plan. D6.3 reports the actions made following the plan and KPIs as described in D6.2
<i>D6.4 Sustainability and Exploitation First Plan</i>	It is expected to be released on Month 20 (<i>March 2018</i>). The strategy for exploitation of project results and for ensuring their sustainability after the end of the project depends on

	effective dissemination strategy. D6.3 updates the plan for the period M19-M36.
<i>D6.5 Sustainability and Exploitation Final Plan</i>	It is expected to be released on Month 35 (<i>June 2019</i>). This deliverable updates the D6.4 and it is also related to D6.2, since successful exploitation and sustainability depends on effective dissemination strategy. D6.3 updates the plan for the period M19-M36.
<i>D6.6 Final Communication and Dissemination Report</i>	It is expected to be released on Month 36 (<i>July 2019</i>). This deliverable will report the activities that will be implemented during the whole project duration, based on the strategy and action plan presented in D6.1 and D6.2 and updated in D6.3

Table 4 : D6.3 Relation with other WP6 deliverables

2 Objectives and Audience of Communication & Dissemination Actions

2.1 Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Actions

- To widely and effectively communicate the project's objectives, methodology, benefits and findings among wide variety of stakeholders, from public bodies who are involved in flood mitigation and response to policy-makers and academics, as well as the general public in order to maximize the project's impact and visibility and to ensure the take-up of the pilot methodologies and tools in the long-term.
- To show how the aims and outcomes of FLOOD-serv are relevant to flood risk management and to people's everyday lives.
- To establish a dialog with those who can contribute to development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of the project results;
- To raise the profile of the organisations carrying out the project at local, national and international level and highlight the European added value of activities supported by Horizon 2020 programme.
- To link with other EU projects funded under the ICT-enabled open government call as well as other international projects and organizations of relevance for the FLOOD-serv project, integrating knowledge coming from these projects, investigating collaboration opportunities and exploiting synergies.
- To spread the word out about the project results and lessons learnt as far as possible in order to enable others to benefit from the activities and experiences of this project and to maximize the impact of research;
- To achieve a return of investment by reaching out to as many potential users of the project results;
- To transfer the research-based knowledge to the ones that can best make use of it
- To generate market demand for the products or services developed;
- To promote the developments of the project to potential end users aiming to attract their attention about the FLOOD-serv solution;
- To prepare the ground for the sustainability and further exploitation of the results beyond the project lifetime.
- To raise public awareness that the EU money are well spent.

2.2 Audience of Communication & Dissemination Actions

The targeted audience that the project's communication and dissemination actions of the FLOOD-serv consortium (*also presented in D6.1 and D6.2*) can be divided into six main categories:

1. **End-users** - Are the ones that direct benefit from the project results;
2. **Decision makers/replication actors** - Are those that have the decision power for the adoption of the project results in the countries where pilot cities will be implemented;
3. **Stakeholders** - Are the ones that have a direct or indirect benefit from the project;
4. **Policy makers** - Are those that can integrate project results into policies;
5. **Funding Authority** - Research Executive Agency (*REA*)/European Commission;
6. **General Public** from EU countries.

Detailed description of each category can be found in **Appendix I**.

3 Tools and Channels

This chapter provides to the reader a detail report about the communication and dissemination tools and channels that the consortium employed during the first 18 months of the project. In parallel it outlines all the actions taken by using these tools and channels within the same period (M1-M18).

3.1 Website

The most important online communication channel, for all kinds of project, is the website. It plays a key role in transmitting the desired messages to target groups and ensures its presence in all available online search engines. In this context, the [FLOOD-serv website](#) was launched in September 2016 (M2) and since then it serves as the major mean of information for communicating with the stakeholders and disseminating its results to a wide audience.

3.1.1 Website Content

It has been regularly updated with project news and results as well as news and events related to the project's topic. Nevertheless, information around the FLOOD-serv such as its objectives, the expected impact of the action, about the consortium, the promotional materials, dissemination activities and so on is available.

In addition, for attracting more traffic at the website and generally gain more visibility for the project, non-scientific articles (*original content*) were written by the consortium partners and uploaded at the FLOOD-serv news section. They can be found are at "[Project News](#)" section and more information is available in the table below.

No.	Partner/s	Month	Article	URL
1.	Gov2u	October 2016	FLOOD-serv project kicks off in Bucharest	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-project-kicks-off-in-bucharest/
2.	CELLENT, GENOVA	December 2016	Workshop in Genova, Italy	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/workshop-genova-italy-2/
3.	Gov2u	December 2016	FLOOD-serv First Newsletter Issue is now available!	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-first-newsletter-issue-now-available/
4.	CELLENT	January 2017	FLOOD-serv Workshop in Tulcea, Romania	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-workshop-tulcea-romania/
5.	CELLENT	January 2017	FLOOD-serv Workshop In Bratislava	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-workshop-bratislava/
6.	CELLENT, ANO, CMVNF	February 2017	Workshop in Famalicão	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/workshop-in-famalicao/

7.	SIVCO	February 2017	A dedicated system to support public authorities in flood emergencies is under construction	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/dedicated-system-support-public-authorities-flood-emergencies-construction-2/
8.	CELLENT, BILBAO, Gov2u	February 2017	Workshop in Bilbao	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/workshop-in-bilbao/
9.	EXDWARF	March 2017	FLOOD-serv signed a memorandum of cooperation with the Slovak Hydro-meteorological Institute (SHMU)	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-signed-memorandum-cooperation-slovak-hydro-meteorological-institute-shmu/
10.	Gov2u, DDNI	March 2017	25th International Symposium "DELTAS and WETLANDS"	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/title-25th-international-symposium-deltas-wetlands/
11.	Gov2u	March 2017	FLOOD-serv Second Newsletter Issue now available!	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-second-newsletter-issue-now-available/
12.	DDNI	April 2017	From reaction to prevention: The power of ICT combined with flood risk management tactics	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/reaction-prevention-power-ict-combined-flood-risk-management-tactics/
13.	IP Tulcea, DDNI, Gov2u	May 2017	FLOOD-serv Project in the International Scientific Event "Deltas and Wetlands"	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-project-international-scientific-event-deltas-wetlands/
14.	Bilbao	June 2017	Getting ready for next flooding	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/getting-ready-next-flooding/
15.	BSK	June 2017	FLOOD-serv in BVS Svet Magazine	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-bvs-svet-magazine/
16.	Gov2u	July 2017	Collaboration with Mobile Age project	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/collaboration-mobile-age-project/
17.	Gov2u	July 2017	Facing future Floods in Europe	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/facing-future-floods-europe/

18.	EXDWARE, BSK	July 2017	FLOOD-serv meets the Mayor of Bratislava	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/flood-serv-meets-mayor-bratislava/
19.	Answer, Gov2u	July 2017	Project Meeting in Tulcea	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/project-meeting-tulcea-2/
20.	Gov2u	October 2017	The FLOOD-serv Project went to Japan!	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/project-news/flood-serv-project-went-japan/

Table 5 : Articles uploaded at Project News – FLOOD-serv website

3.1.2 Site Map

The **menu bar** of the FLOOD-serv website is consisted by six sections (*Home section included*) and 20 subsections. The **“About”** has 7 subsections which namely are: *“Our Objectives”, “The Pilots”, “Work Overview”, “Expected Impact”, “Consortium”, “Meet the team”, “Advisory Board”*.

Figure 1 : About section – FLOOD-serv website

The **“News”** section has 4 subsections: *“Project News”, “News from the Web”, “Events”, and “Videos”*.

Figure 2 : News section – FLOOD-serv website

The **“Results”** section has 5 subsections: *“Deliverables”, “Publications’, “Similar Projects’, “FLOOD-serv System” and “Dissemination”*.

Figure 3 : Results section – FLOOD-serv website

The “Press Kit” section has the following 4 subsections: “Newsletter”, “Press Releases”, “Promotional Materials” and “Presentations”.

Figure 4 : Press Kit section – FLOOD-serv website

Lastly, the section “Contact us” contains a contact form by which the website visitors are able to send their message and communicate with the consortium.

3.1.3 Website Analytics

The success of the activities undertaken for maintaining and updating the FLOOD-serv website is highly interrelated with its performance during the reporting period. For this reason, this report includes the performance measurement of the website (*analytics*) which is presented within the current section. The analytics are provided by the AWstats service and the glossary of terms used can be found in **Appendix III**.

No.	Month	Unique Visitors	Number of Visits	Pages	Hits	Bandwidth
M1	Aug 2016	13	48	900	4,154	76.84 MB
M2	Sep 2016	60	215	23,127	261,305	4.96 GB
M3	Oct 2016	314	759	6,781	40,499	2.21 GB
M4	Nov 2016	264	775	9,049	28,028	343.04 MB

M5	Dec 2016	371	927	7,806	31,052	292.15 MB
M6	Jan 2017	498	936	6,211	23,380	244.18 MB
M7	Feb 2017	2,741	3,331	16,909	43,065	452.65 MB
M8	Mar 2017	1,076	1,526	16,173	51,503	596.24 MB
M9	Apr 2017	1,500	1,869	13,145	20,460	300.10 MB
M10	May 2017	830	1,555	11,698	19,104	317.27 MB
M11	Jun 2017	1,343	2,208	16,611	32,738	339.00 MB
M12	Jul 2017	955	1,468	16,562	39,11	496.26 MB
M13	Aug 2017	920	1,400	7,658	18,351	247.89 MB
M14	Sep 2017	965	1,578	7,518	18,791	273.73 MB
M15	Oct 2017	1,196	1,829	10,507	33,726	480.33 MB
M16	Nov 2017	3,410	4,070	15,596	57,585	1.56 GB
M17	Dec 2017	1,380	1,939	7,319	19,124	556.32 MB
M18	Jan 2018	1,240	1,589	6,633	21,915	682.05 MB
Total in M18		19,076	26,622	200,203	680,940	578,535GB

Table 6 : FLOOD-serv Website Analytics by AWstats

Figure 5 : Website Unique Visitors (M1-M18)

Figure 6 : Website Pages (M1-M18)

Figure 7 : Number of Visits (M1-M18)

3.2 Social Media

Social media are powerful and significant tools for communication with a wider audience as through one source many recipients can be reached. For greater outreach and also taking advantage of the benefits that these means offer, the FLOOD-serv accounts in Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+ and the project’s page on Facebook were created from the very start of its lifecycle.

The Facebook page as well as the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts were created in M1 (August 2016) and the Google+ account in M2 (September 2016). Additionally, in M6 (January 2017)

the Community of Interest LinkedIn group was created (*based on the FLOOD-serv LinkedIn account*) in order to promote the FLOOD-serv results in a more targeted manner concerning the pilot sites.

The project's social media accounts were updated with posts of:

- FLOOD-serv **publications**;
- FLOOD-serv **events** organized by the consortium;
- FLOOD-serv **e-newsletter issues**;
- Non-scientific articles written by the FLOOD-serv consortium and published at the project's website;
- Results from **other EU funded projects** that respectively support FLOOD-serv by sharing information about it;
- FLOOD-serv profiles on **digital publishing platforms** (*i.e. Issuu, SlideShare and Scribd*);
- **Other project news** (*participation in public events, presence in press and media etc.*);
- News and events related to the project's topic.

More audience was attracted and visibility was increased by adding the following hashtags in the aforementioned types of posts:

- #FloodEmergency
- #MobileTechnologies
- #OpenGovernment
- #SocialMedia
- #AwarenessService
- #Transparency
- #CitizenEmpowerment
- #EU_Project
- #H2020
- Locations of pilot sites
- Other words relevant with project's publications
- Official hashtags of public events where consortium partners presented the project

3.2.1 Facebook Page

Facebook is an online social media and social networking service. After registering to use the site, users can create a user profile indicating their name, occupation, schools attended and so on. Users can add other users as "friends", exchange messages, post status updates and digital photos, share digital videos and links, use various software applications ("*apps*"), and receive notifications when others update their profiles or make posts.¹ The FLOOD-serv Facebook page was created in August 2016 (*M1*) and posts started to be made with the launch of the project's website (*end of September 2016 – M2*). It has been promoted through the project's website, newsletter issues and partners' networks. The number of page likes in Y1 was 71 and increased in 118 in M18.

¹ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Facebook> (Wikipedia)

D6.3 First Communication and Dissemination Report & Updated Plan

Figure 8 : FLOOD-serv Facebook Page

Overview of Facebook Page	
Created in	August 2016 (M1)
URL	https://www.facebook.com/FLOODservEU/
Mention	@FLOODservEU
Page Likes in M6	54
Page Likes in M12 (Y1)	71
Page Likes in M18	118

Table 7 : Overview of Facebook Page

Figure 9 : Post Reach – Facebook Page

Figure 10 : Growth of Facebook Page Likes

3.2.2 Twitter Profile

Twitter is an online news and social networking service where users post and interact with messages, "tweets", restricted to 280 characters for all *languages (except Japanese, Korean and Chinese that have limit of 140 characters)*. Registered users can post tweets, but those who are unregistered can only read them. ² The profile of FLOOD-serv project on Twitter was created in August 2016 (M1) and its first post was made at the end of September 2016 for announcing the launch of the project’s website. By the end of Y1 this profile had 42 followers, 226 profile visits and 6,605 tweet impressions. These numbers were increased in M18 to 50 followers, 277 profile visits and 8,933 tweet impressions.

Figure 11 : FLOOD-serv Twitter Profile

² Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Twitter> (Wikipedia)

Overview of Twitter Account		
Created in	August 2016 (M1)	
URL	https://twitter.com/FLOODservEU	
Mention	@FLOODservEU	
Followers	in M6	28
	in M12 (Y1)	42
	in M18	50
Tweet Impressions	in M6	1,679
	in M12	6,605
	in M18	8,933
Profile visits	in M6	147
	in M12	226
	in M18	277

Table 8 : Overview of Twitter account

Figure 12 : Tweet Impressions

Figure 13 : New Followers per Month

Figure 14 : Growth of Twitter Followers

3.2.3 LinkedIn Account

LinkedIn is a business-and employment-oriented social networking service that operates via websites and mobile apps. It is mainly used for professional networking, including employers posting jobs and job seekers posting their CVs. LinkedIn allows members (*both workers and employers*) to create profiles and "connections" to each other in an online social network which may represent real-world professional relationships. Members can invite anyone (*whether an existing member or not*) to become a connection. The "gated-access approach" (*where contact with any professional requires either an existing relationship or an introduction through a contact of theirs*) is intended to build trust among the service's members.³ The LinkedIn account of the project was created in M1 and its first post was made at the end of September 2016 for

³ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LinkedIn> (Wikipedia)

announcing the launch of the project’s website. In Y1 the connections of the account were 107 and in M18 were increased to 131.

Figure 15 : FLOOD-serv LinkedIn Account

Overview of LinkedIn Account	
Created in	August 2016 (M1)
URL	https://www.linkedin.com/in/flood-serv-project-eu-b0361b126/
Mention	@FLOODservEU
Connections in M12 (Y1)	107
Connections in M18	131

Table 9 : Overview of LinkedIn account

3.2.4 Google+ Account

Google+ is an Internet based social network that is owned and operated by Google.⁴ The FLOOD-serv account was created in September 2016 and first posts were made in October 2016 for announcing the launch of the project’s website and the release of the project’s Factsheet. However, Google+ is a social media network that is not very popular to social media users and thus consortium’s expectations for spreading FLOOD-serv messages is very low. Within this framework in section 5 “Performance Measurement of Dissemination Activities” of the deliverable D6.2 the set indication of success for this account was 10 followers. The measurement of connections in Y1 showed 4 and in M18 raised to 5.

⁴ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Google%2B> (Wikipedia)

Figure 16 : FLOOD-serv Google+ Account

Overview of Google+ Account	
Created in	M2 (September 2016)
URL	https://plus.google.com/u/0/115871353144527478058
Connections in M12 (Y1)	4
Connections in M18	5

Table 10 : Overview of Google+ account

3.3 Newsletter

The newsletter is a dissemination tool (see **D6.2 Dissemination Plan**) that assists WP6 in reaching the target audiences and conveying to them the major FLOOD-serv developments and results with main aim to attract their attention and engage them.

During the reporting period we published 3 newsletter issues in M5, M8 and M12 that followed the activity of the project and the produced results. The design was made by Gov2u with tailor made approach for each issue that was depended from the unique content of each one. All issues were created with easy-to read content by WP6 leader while all partners contributed and gave feedback. In order to avoid “spamming” the target audiences with little content we published the first issue in M5 (*December 2016*) not in M4 as foreseen in D6.2. Moreover, for the same reason we did not publish in November 2017 the planned issue as there was not much information to share. Nevertheless, the fourth issue will be published in March 2018.

Contact lists of stakeholders from pilot sites and across Europe have been created in order to disseminate the FLOOD-serv news. Also, 25 individuals have voluntarily subscribed through the respective form at project’s website. For distributing (*via email*) the e-newsletter issues we use the free service of [Moosend](#). It is an email marketing service provider where its users can manage their mailing lists, craft their newsletters, schedule their delivery and track and evaluate their performance. All newsletter issues can be found at project’s website on section “Press Kit”, subsection “[Newsletter](#)”.

A short description of each newsletter issue as well as their performance is presented in the sections that follow.

3.3.1 Newsletter Issue No.1

The [first newsletter issue](#) of the project was published in December 2016 (M5) and briefly introduced to the readers the project. Additionally, the very first FLOOD-serv results were presented. The performance of the first issue was measured by Moosend.

<i>Measured indicators</i>	<i>Achieved</i>
Unsubscribe rate	0.7%
Unique opens:	11.0%
Link clicks:	0.9%
Bounce rate for the email version of the newsletter	4.4%
Delivery rate for the email version of the newsletter	5/10 (https://www.mail-tester.com/web-wrnej)
Spam complaint rate for the email version of the newsletter	0

Table 11 : Analytics of Newsletter Issue No.1

3.3.2 Newsletter Issue No.2

The [second newsletter issue](#) was published in March 2017 (M8) and had as main topic the WP3 workshops conducted in pilot sites. In addition, the project was embraced by the local press and media in pilot sites and we presented what they said about FLOOD-serv. The performance of the second issue is showed in **Table 12**.

<i>Measured indicators</i>	<i>Achieved</i>
Unsubscribe rate	0.8%
Unique opens:	17.3%
Link clicks:	0.8%
Bounce rate for the email version of the newsletter	0.8%
Delivery rate for the email version of the newsletter	10/10 (https://www.mail-tester.com/web-v69ce)
Spam complaint rate for the email version of the newsletter	0

Table 12 : Analytics of Newsletter Issue No.2

3.3.3 Newsletter Issue No.3

The [third newsletter issue](#) was published in July 2017 (M12) and results of the project were presented. The performance of the third issue is displayed in **table 13**.

<i>Measured indicators</i>	<i>Achieved</i>
Unsubscribe rate	2.7%
Unique opens:	19.7%
Link clicks:	1.2%
Bounce rate for the email version of the newsletter	1.4%
Delivery rate for the email version of the newsletter	10/10 (https://www.mail-tester.com/web-i76q3)
Spam complaint rate for the email version of the newsletter	0

Table 13 : Analytics of Newsletter Issue No.3

3.4 Press Releases

A press release consists written communication mostly with members of news media with the purpose of announcing news that would interest the general public, in our case the project's stakeholders. It is considered as a very efficient tool for disseminating FLOOD-serv developments since their distribution to a large number of recipients (*media outlets, similar organizations, similar initiatives and projects, academia, communities and networks, etc.*) help promote the project at local and pan-European level.

During the reporting period eight press releases (*see Table 14*) have been published by the project partners. For avoiding repetition of information all links are available at the current deliverable in chapter 4, section **4.5.1 List of Media Coverage** .Press releases will be published throughout the project's lifecycle.

<i>No.</i>	<i>Title of press release</i>	<i>Language</i>	<i>Published in</i>
1.	Camara adere a projeto europeu para prevencao do risco de cheias	Portuguese	O Povo Famalicense (<i>newspaper</i>)
2.	Famalicao participa em projeto europeu para prevencao do risco de cheias	Portuguese	Opinião Pública (<i>newspaper</i>)
3.	Kraj posilňuje protipovodňovú ochranu	Slovak	Teraz, 24hod, regional press Pezinsko
4.	BSK: Konferencia o ochrane vody	Slovak	BSK website

5.	Raca dostane viac ochrany pred vodou	Slovak	Račiansky výber (<i>monthly magazine</i>)
6.	Natural disasters – major concern for European authorities	English	Nine o'clock
7.	Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	Romanian	Agerpres, Comunicate de Presa, Web PR, AMOS News, HotNews, Ziare pe net, Comunicate de a faceri, Agora, Live PR, PR wave, STIRI EVENIMENTE, Press mania, M-security NEWS, Science HotNews, Communicate online, Curierul de Ramnic, Cronica de Iasi, infoBRASOV.net, SANSA News, 008.ro, pescurt.ro, Centrul de presa
8.	Floods are consuming 2.1% from Romania's GNP	English	American Chamber of Commerce in Romania

Table 14 : List of published press releases

3.5 Promotional Materials

Promotional materials (*i.e. brochure, flyer, poster, factsheet*) are a collection of dissemination and promotional tools used to support the project's identity, to raise awareness and visibility of the project, to attract and motivate stakeholders to get engaged to the project, as well as to be distributed to audiences during the project's presentation in events, workshops and conferences.

Their content was prepared by WP6 leader and circulated to the consortium for review. Later on, Gov2u designed, created and made them available in digital format at the project's website (*see section Press Kit, subsection [Promotional Materials](#)*). The produced, so far, materials are:

- **Factsheet** (EN);
- **Brochure** (EN);
- **Flyer** (EN, ES, IT, SK, PT, RO);
- **Poster** (EN, ES, IT, SK, PT, RO).

Figure 17 : Sample of FLOOD-serv Promotional Materials

Figure 18 : Flyer's versions (ES, IT, SK, PT, RO)

Figure 19 : Poster's versions (ES, IT, SK, PT, RO)

The project's flyer as well as its poster have been translated by the respective partners in Spanish (*Answare, BILBAO*), Italian (*GENOVA*), Portuguese (*ANO, CMVNF*), Slovak (*Exdwarf, BSK*) and Romanian (*SIVECO, IP Tulcea, DDNI*). The task of translating the materials and the work division was discussed via emails and consortium's conference calls. Partners from the same countries worked together for the translations and the content's review in order to achieve the best outcome. The promotional materials have been printed upon partners' request (*for workshops conducted in pilot cities*). Additionally, the overall presentation of the project has been created and distributed to all partners.

All the official templates of the project (*Deliverable template, Power point presentation template, Letterhead, Press release template, Meeting minutes, Meetings/ ConCall Agenda Template*) have been produced and distributed to the consortium in order to ensure that all FLOOD-serv's communication activities are consistent with the visual identify of the project.

Screenshots of the promotional materials in English version can be found in **Appendix II**.

3.6 Digital Publishing Platforms

Electronic publishing (also referred to as *e-publishing* or *digital publishing* or *online publishing*) includes the digital publication of e-books, digital magazines, and the development of digital libraries and catalogues.⁵

In our project’s case we created profiles in Issuu, Scribd and LinkedIn Slideshare for digital publishing and they will serve as dissemination tools for promoting the FLOOD-serv outcomes i.e. public deliverables (*approved by REA*), publications, the newsletter issues and promotional materials.

3.6.1 Issuu

Issuu is a free electronic publishing platform for magazines, catalogs, and newspapers.⁶ The FLOOD-serv profile was created in November 2016 (M4) where the promotional materials in English version were initially uploaded and the months that followed it was enriched with the materials translated in partners’ language and project’s publications. It can be found at: <https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject>

Figure 20 : Issuu profile

⁵ Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electronic_publishing (Wikipedia)

⁶ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Issuu> (Wikipedia)

The platform provides some free statistics concerning the overall performance of the profile as well as per published item.

Lifetime Statistics for **FLOOD-serv EU project**

You have been a member since November 10th 2016

Figure 21 : Overall performance – Issuu profile

The explanation of the metrics terms (*as given by Issuu*) that are showcased in **Figure 21** is:

- **Reads:** Counted each time a user opened a publication for more than 2 seconds.
- **Impressions:** Counted each time a publication was displayed to a user in an embedded or on Issuu.
- **Followers:** The number of users following your Issuu profile.
- **Likes:** The number of users following your Issuu profile.
- **Shares:** The number of times a user shared your publication from Issuu.
- **Link-outs:** Number of clicks on a publisher made link.
- **Average time spent:** The average time readers spent reading this publication
- **Read time:** The total time readers spend reading this publication

Figure 22 : Readers around the world – Issuu profile

The list with the published items on the FLOOD-serv profile is presented in the table below.

S/N	Title of the published item	URL	Type	Reads	Impressions	Average time spend	Read time
1.	Brochure of FLOOD-serv EU Project	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flood-serv_brochure	Marketing Material	33	138	0:02:29	1:22:08
2.	Factsheet of FLOOD-serv EU Project	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flood-serv_factsheet	Marketing Material	16	261	0:01:33	0:24:57
3.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (English)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flyer_for-web	Marketing Material	13	49	0:01:48	0:23:27
4.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Spanish)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flyer_for-web-spanish	Marketing Material	10	36	0:02:29	0:24:53
5.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Portuguese)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flyer_for-web-portuguese	Marketing Material	6	33	0:03:51	0:23:10
6.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Romanian)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flyer_for-web-romanian	Marketing Material	17	65	0:02:36	0:44:13
7.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Italian)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flyer_for-web-italian	Marketing Material	4	52	0:04:43	0:18:54
8.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Slovak)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flyer_for-web-slovak	Marketing Material	6	29	0:02:27	0:14:42

9.	FLOOD-serv Poster	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/poster_v5_for-web	Marketing Material	3	84	0:02:42	0:08:07
10.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Spanish)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/poster_es_webv	Marketing Material	1	12	0:07:40	0:07:40
11.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Romanian)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/floodserv_poster_romanian	Marketing Material	1	13	0:07:40	0:07:40
12.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Italian)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/floodserv_poster_italian	Marketing Material	1	13	0:08:40	0:08:40
13.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Portuguese)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/floodserv_poster_portuguese	Marketing Material	1	13	0:08:40	0:08:40
14.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Slovak)	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/floodserv_poster_slovak	Marketing Material	1	14	0:12:40	0:12:40
15.	Flood services legislative approach in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management floods	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/docs/flood_services_legislative_approach	Paper	15	91	0:02:39	0:39:54
16.	Flood services needs in	https://issuu.com/flood-serveuproject/	Study	8	78	0:02:23	0:19:08

<p>the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management - FLOOD-serv project</p>	<p>docs/flood_services_needs_in_the_context</p>					
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Table 15 : Published items on Issuu

3.6.2 LinkedIn Slideshare

LinkedIn SlideShare is a Web 2.0–based slide hosting service where users can upload files privately or publicly in the following file formats: PowerPoint, PDF, Keynote or OpenDocument presentations. Slide decks can then be viewed on the site itself, on hand held devices or embedded on other sites. Although the website is primarily a slide hosting service, it also supports documents, PDFs, videos and webinars. It also provides to the users the ability to rate, comment on, and share the uploaded content.⁷

The FLOOD-serv profile on Slideshare was created in September 2016 (M2) and can be found at: <https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU>

Figure 23 : Slideshare profile

The profile’s analytics for the whole reporting period, provided by the LinkedIn Slideshare, are presented in the figures below (see figures 25, 26, 27). Figure 24 consists an exemption as the profile summary is provided by the analytics service for a period of a year maximum. The

⁷ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SlideShare> (Wikipedia)

options that the user has for analytics is one week, one month, three months, 6 months and one year.

Figure 24 : FLOOD-serv Slideshare profile summary (Feb. 17' – Jan. 18')

Top content	
Name	Views
FLOOD-serv project Brochure	56
FLOOD-serv Poster	43
FLOOD-serv Flyer (Portuguese)	33
FLOOD-serv Flyer (Slovak)	31
FLOOD-serv Flyer (Italian)	26

Figure 25 : Top content – Slideshare profile

Top countries	
Name	Views
United States	161
Greece	107
Canada	10
Sri Lanka	8
Philippines	5

Figure 26 : Top countries – Slideshare profile

Figure 27 : Traffic sources – Slideshare profile

S/N	Title of published item	URL	Type	Total Views
1.	Brochure of FLOOD-serv EU Project	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-project-brochure	Marketing Material	89
2.	Factsheet of FLOOD-serv EU Project	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-factsheetforweb	Marketing Material	54
3.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (English)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-flyer-english	Marketing Material	32
4.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Spanish)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-flyer-spanish	Marketing Material	27
5.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Portuguese)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-flyer-portuguese	Marketing Material	37
6.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Romanian)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-flyer-romanian	Marketing Material	28
7.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Italian)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-flyer-italian	Marketing Material	28
8.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Slovak)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-flyer-slovak	Marketing Material	33

9.	FLOOD-serv Poster	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-poster	Marketing Material	48
10.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Spanish)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-poster-in-spanish	Marketing Material	6
11.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Romanian)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-poster-in-romanian	Marketing Material	3
12.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Italian)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-poster-italian	Marketing Material	3
13.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Portuguese)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-poster-portuguese	Marketing Material	4
14.	FLOOD-serv Poster (Slovak)	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-poster-slovak	Marketing Material	6
15.	Flood services legislative approach in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management floods	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/flood-services-legislative-approach-in-the-context-of-danube-delta-area-flood-risk-management-floodserv-project	Paper	7
16.	Flood services needs in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management – FLOOD-serv project	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/flood-services-needs-in-the-context-of-danube-delta-area-flood-risk-management-flood-serv-project	Study	11
17.	FLOOD-serv Brochure Updated	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/floodserv-brochure-updated	Marketing Material	7
18.	Factsheet of FLOOD-serv EU Project Updated	https://www.slideshare.net/FLOODservProjectEU/factsheet-of-floodserv-eu-project-updated	Marketing Material	9

Table 16 : Published items on Slideshare

3.6.3 Scribd

Scribd is a digital library, e-book and audiobook subscription service.⁸ The profile of FLOOD-serv was created in November 2016 (M4) and can be found at:

<https://www.scribd.com/user/337345109/FLOOD-serv-Project>

Figure 28 : Scribd profile

At the current profile we have uploaded 11 items (*publications and promotional materials*) that are freely accessible to anyone interested for reading and/or downloading them. The following table lists the published items and their analytics (*views*).

S/N	Title of published item	URL	Type	Total Views
1.	FLOOD-serv Brochure	https://www.scribd.com/document/330278498/FLOOD-serv-Brochure	Marketing Material	26
2.	FLOOD-serv Factsheet	https://www.scribd.com/document/330278415/FLOOD-serv-Factsheet	Marketing Material	16
3.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (English)	https://www.scribd.com/document/332793541/FLOOD-serv-Flyer-English	Marketing Material	14
4.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Spanish)	https://www.scribd.com/document/338217469/FLOOD-serv-Flyer-Spanish	Marketing Material	2
5.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Portuguese)	https://www.scribd.com/document/338217415/FLOOD-serv-Flyer-Portuguese	Marketing Material	4

⁸ Source: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scribd> (Wikipedia)

6.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Romanian)	https://www.scribd.com/document/338217472/FLOOD-serv-Flyer-Romanian	Marketing Material	3
7.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Italian)	https://www.scribd.com/document/338217418/FLOOD-serv-Flyer-Italian	Marketing Material	4
8.	FLOOD-serv Flyer (Slovak)	https://www.scribd.com/document/338217480/FLOOD-serv-Flyer-Slovak	Marketing Material	4
9.	FLOOD-serv Poster	https://www.scribd.com/document/338217771/FLOOD-Serv-Poster-English	Marketing Material	4
10.	Flood services legislative approach in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management floods	https://www.scribd.com/document/370774284/Flood-Services-Legislative-Approach-in-the-Context-of-Danube-Delta-Area-Flood-Risk-Management-FLOOD-serv-Project	Paper	7
11.	Flood services needs in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management – FLOOD-serv project	https://www.scribd.com/document/370778591/Flood-Services-Needs-in-the-Context-of-Danube-Delta-Area-Flood-Risk-Management-FLOOD-serv-Project	Study	12

Table 17 : Published items on Scribd

4 Communication and Dissemination Activities

During the first 18 month of project's implementation the consortium organized workshops in the pilot cities, participated in third party events, contacted directly with stakeholders, gave interviews to press and generally promoted the project through media. The sections that follow provide in detail all the related information concerning the communication and dissemination activities performed within the reporting period (*August 2016 - January 2018*).

4.1 Organization of events

4.1.1 List of the FLOOD-serv events

No.	Partner (s)	Name of the event	Date	Location	Description of the event (type, aim, size of the audience, type of the audience)
1.	CELLENT, GENOVA, Answare, ANO	WP3 Workshop in Genova	6 - 7 December 2016	Genova, Italy	<p>Aim: Provision of an overview to the stakeholders of the pilot in Genova. Workshop D3.1 related to the clarification of Genova's user requirements</p> <p>Size of Audience: 25 participants (24 physical presence +1 online)</p> <p>Type of Audience: Project partners and local stakeholders.</p>
2.	CELLENT, IP Tulcea, DDNI, SIVECO	WP3 Workshop in Tulcea	12-13 December 2016	Tulcea, Romania	<p>Aim: Provision of an overview to the stakeholders of the pilot in Tulcea. Workshop D3.1 related to the clarification of Tulcea's requirements</p> <p>Size of Audience: 20 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience: Project partners and local stakeholders.</p>
3.	CELLENT, BSK, Exdwarf, Answare	WP3 Workshop in Bratislava	14-15 December 2016	Bratislava , Slovakia	<p>Aim: Technical partners presented potential systems and their possible use within the pilot</p>

					<p>in Slovakia. The workshop D3.1 was related to the clarification of Bratislava's requirements</p> <p>Size of Audience: 26 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience: Project partners and local stakeholders</p>
4.	BSK, Exdwarf	TV interview in TV Bratislava channel	15 December 2016	Bratislava, BSK	<p>Aim: Present the project and the pilot in BSK through the local media. Karin Bartošová from BSK and Tomas Koren from Exdwarf gave interview.</p> <p>Size of Audience: The interview was given to TV Bratislava channel (<i>1 reporter and the crew</i>). The actual audience was the viewers of the TV Bratislava channel.</p> <p>Type of Audience: Local Media</p>
5.	ANO, CELLENT, Bilbao, SIVECO, Answare	WP3 Workshop in Bilbao	17 – 18 January 2017	Bilbao, Spain	<p>Aim: Provision of an overview to the stakeholders of the pilot in Bilbao. Workshop D3.1 related to the clarification of Bilbao's requirements</p> <p>Size of Audience: 29 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience: Project partners and local stakeholders.</p>
6.	CELLENT, ANO, Answare, CMVNF, SIVECO	WP3 Workshop in Famalicão Workshop	26-27 January 2017	Vila Nova de Famalicao, Portugal	<p>Aim: Provision of an overview to the stakeholders of the pilot in Vila Nova de Famalicao. Workshop D3.1 related to the clarification of Vila Nova</p>

					<p>de Famalicão requirements. Dissemination activities for other stakeholders that participated.</p> <p>Size of Audience: 24 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience: Project partners and local stakeholders</p>
7.	BSK, Exdwarf	World Water Day - Press conference within the event	22 March 2017	Bratislava , Slovakia	<p>Aim: Presentation about the project the pilot in BSK, current status and progress in the project. Interview with Katarina Vargová with local media.</p> <p>Size of Audience: -</p> <p>Type of Audience: Local media</p>
8.	Exdwarf	Mayors Workshop	30 March 2017	Bratislava , Slovakia	<p>Aim: Community buildup, networking and dissemination.</p> <p>Size of Audience: 10 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience: Mayors of flood-risk areas in Bratislava, Slovak Water Enterprise, BSK</p>
9.	GENOVA	Seminar "COMUNITA' E RISCHI NATURALI"	23 May 2017	Municipio Medio Levante – Genova, Italy	<p>Aim: Dissemination of the project and its goals to involve citizen for active contributions. http://www.comune.genova.it/node/77277</p> <p>Size of Audience 19 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience:</p>

					Local stakeholders and citizens
10.	Exdwarf and BSK	Pilot workshop	19-20 September 2018	Office of Bratislava Self-Governin g Region, Bratislava , Slovakia	<p>Aim: Workshop for pilot preparation,</p> <p>Size of Audience: 19 participants from consortium and Slovak stakeholders</p> <p>Type of Audience: Involved key project stakeholders from Slovakia, incl. mayors of pilot municipalities Bratislava Raca and Bratislava Devin who gave presentations.</p>
11.	GENOVA	pre-test APP training <i>in collaboration with UNIGE - DAD</i>	25 October 2017	MUNICIPI O BASSA VAL BISAGNO III	<p>Aim: a) Presentation of the pilot project activities and its output. B) Dissemination of the pre-test c) Training for use of the pre-test APP (Mugugn.app)</p> <p>Size of Audience: 25 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience: Mayors of municipalities around Genova area, civil protection representatives, local associations and organizations, representatives from academia</p>
12.	GENOVA	Presentatio n of Genoa pilot	26 October 2017	UNIGE DAD	<p>Aim: Presentation of the activities and the output of the Genoa Pilot Project;</p> <p>Size of Audience: 10 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience</p>

					Students of the University of Genoa (UNIGE – DAD) – II class Bachelor’s Degree in science of architecture
13.	GENOVA	PRE-TEST app technical presentation and training on hydrological risk <i>(in collaboration with UNIGE – DAD)</i>	6 November 2017	Ordine degli Ingegneri di Genova-sua sede (headquarters)	<p>Aim:</p> <p>a) Presentation of the activities and the output of the Genoa Pilot Project; b) Training about the hydrological risk of the territory; c) Technical presentation of the PRE-TEST app (Mugugn.app)</p> <p>Size of Audience:</p> <p>48 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience:</p> <p>Engineers</p>
14.	GENOVA	PRE-TEST APP technical presentation <i>(in collaboration with UNIGE – DAD)</i>	21 November 2017 and 15 December 2017	Istituto PROFESSORONALE TECNICO AGRARIO “MARSANO”	<p>Aim:</p> <p>a) Presentation of the activities and the output of the Genoa Pilot Project; b) Technical presentation of the PRE-TEST app (Mugugn.app)</p> <p>Size of Audience:</p> <p>61 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience:</p> <p>Students of TECNICO AGRARIO “MARSANO” (n. 2 IV class and 1 V class)</p>
15.	GENOVA	PRE-TEST APP technical presentation <i>(in collaboration with UNIGE – DAD)</i>	01 December 2017	Liceo Classico Statale “Andrea Doria”	<p>Aim:</p> <p>a) Presentation of the activities and the output of the Genoa Pilot Project; b) Technical presentation of the PRE-TEST APP (Mugugn.app)</p> <p>Size of Audience:</p> <p>49 participants</p> <p>Type of Audience:</p> <p>Students of LICEO CLASSICO STATALE “Andrea Doria”</p>

					Genova (n.1 I class and 1 III class)
16.	ANO	Workshop on Public Procurement	9 November 2017	Lisbon	Workshop for around 100 public authorities and businesses, organized by ANO
17.	ANO	Workshop on Public Procurement	14 December 2017	Porto	Workshop for around 100 public authorities and businesses, organized by ANO
18.	ANO	Workshop on Public Procurement	23 January 2018	Lisbon	Workshop for around 100 public authorities and businesses, organized by ANO
19.	ANO	Workshop on Public Procurement	30 January 2018	Porto	Workshop for around 100 public authorities and businesses, organized by ANO

Table 18 : List of FLOOD-serv events

4.1.2 Highlights from the FLOOD-serv events

Figure 29 : WP3 Workshops in pilot sites

Beyond the WP3 workshops which were attended also by citizens and stakeholders and assisted in dissemination activities, on May 23rd of 2017 the municipality of Genova organised in the City Hall n. VIII, a public meeting under the title: “[*Communities and natural hazards*](#) (*“Comunità e rischi naturali”*) – presentation of FLOOD-serv, an European project for the territory”. The aim of this public meeting was to illustrate the project in the local authorities

and private stakeholders and increase the involvement of the citizen, raise the visibility dissemination activities and ask for further support from the aforementioned target groups.

Figure 30 : “Comunità e rischi naturali” event (Genova)

Additionally, a series of presentations (*PRE-TEST app technical presentation*) about the Genova pilot were organized by the Municipality of Genova with great success from November to December of 2017.

Figure 31 : PRE-TEST app technical presentations (Genova)

4.2 Participation in Third Party Events

4.2.1 List of the FLOOD-serv participation in third party events

No.	Partner	Name of the event	Date	Location of the event (city, country)	Description of the event (type, aim, size of the audience, type of the audience)
1.	ANO , Exdwarf	ICT Proposers day 2016 - Bratislava	26-27 October 2016	Bratislava, Slovakia	The event focused on the Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2016-17 in the field of Information & Communication Technologies. It offered a unique and exceptional opportunity to build quality partnerships with academics, researchers, industrial stakeholders, SMEs and government actors from all over Europe
2.	Answare	Meteorological Technology World Expo 2016	27 September 2016	Madrid, Spain	https://eko-eu.com/events/meteorological-technology-world-expo-2016-madrid-spain-27-09-2016-till-27-09-2016
3.	BSK	"Synergies between European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) & Research and Innovation Funding"	8 March 2017	Brussels, Belgium	http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu .
4.	BSK	Smart Region Conference 2.0, Helsinki	1-2 June 2017	Helsinki, Finland	http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/conferences/smart_regions_2017/
5.	Exdwarf	Cities and Water conference	25 October 2017	Bratislava, Slovakia	Programme: Cities & Water Security, Cities & the River, Cities & Smart water management.

					Aim: Networking and FLOOD-serv dissemination Size: large, international Type of audience: Local Mayors and Ministers, policy makers, representatives from: European Environment agency, Integrated Water Assessment, UNESCO, water management.
6.	Exdwarf	World Water Day	22 March 2017	Bratislava, Slovakia	FLOOD-serv project propagation, mixed audience mostly from BSK and Bratislava Water Company (BVS)
7.	Exdwarf	EC Communication Campaign on H2020 financial rules	07 February 2017	Bratislava, Slovakia	EC communication campaign aimed at H2020 financial rules presentation and networking other projects. Size: large, national
8.	IP Tulcea,	Water and Wetlands	18-21 May 2017	Tulcea, Romania	Presentation of the paper <i>"Flood Services legislative approach in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management– FLOOD-serv Project"</i>
9.	DDNI	Water and Wetlands	18-21 May 2017	Tulcea, Romania	Presentation of the study <i>"Flood Services needs in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management– Flood Serv Project"</i>
10.	SIVECO	Supporting the implementation of eGovernment at regional and local level	15 November 2016	Brussels, Belgium	Organized by European Commission (DG CONNECT) Addressed to regional and local public administrations implement the eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020

11.	SIVECO	SMART CITY WORLD CONGRESS, (Dan Tuhar)	14-16 November 2016	Barcelona, Spain	SCEWC international summit of discussion about the link between urban reality and technological revolution, 591 exhibitors, 600 cities, 420
12.	SIVECO	ICT for Water Management: Enabling Smart Data.	20 January 2017	Bucharest, Romania	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/ict-for-water-management-enabling-smart-data-tickets-3561820501
13.	SIVECO	Open Forum / UEFISCDI	3 February 2017	Bucharest, Romania	http://uefiscdi.gov.ro/articole/4840/Open-Forum.html
14.	SIVECO	Lead Applicants Seminar - 2nd call for proposals - Interreg Danube	9 February 2017	Budapest, Hungary	http://www.interreg-danube.eu/calls/calls-for-proposals/lead-applicants-seminar-2nd-call
15.	SIVECO	Trust in Digital Life Working Group Meeting	23-24 May 2017	Heidelberg, Germany	https://trustindigitallife.eu/wp-content/uploads/TDL-Heidelberg-Working-Group-Programme.pdf
16.	SIVECO	LIFE Closer to you - LIFE CAPACITY BUILDING	18 July 2017	Bucharest, Romania	http://www.ccib.ro/ro/CCIB/1/0/626/programul+lilfe+%E2%80%93+al+comisi ei+europene.html
17.	Exdwarf	EC Communication Campaign on H2020 Financial Rules	18 October 2017	Bratislava, Slovakia	Workshop, seminar with approximately 70 attendees. Most of them participate in H2020 projects (SMEs, corporate, academia, public, NGOs) <i>with local support of Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information</i>
18.	Exdwarf, BSK	Conference Bratislava Smart Region	17 October 2017	Bratislava, Slovakia	Smart cities conference with mixed audience incl. public and SMEs. Focus –

		BSK			smart solutions for cities and region, size of audience 100+, propagation of Floodserv among conference visitors, project flyers
19.	GENOVA	SALONE ORIENTAMENTI Open Maps per la Scuola: il Geoportale, i servizi e gli openDATA cartografici della regione Liguria”	14 November 2017	SALONE ORIENTAMENTI Magazzini del Cotone Porto Antico GENOVA	Promotion of the Pilot project and the pre-test APP (mugugn.app)
20.	GENOVA	“Linux day” GENOVA	27 October 2017	GREAT CAMPUS Parco scientifico e tecnologico - Genova	Promotion of the Pilot project and the pre-test APP (mugugn.app) in the “Corner : GFOSS & OpenData in Regione Liguria- Liguria Digitale, Sviluppo Sistemi Amministrativi e Territoriali”
23.	ANO	ENEG 2017	21 to 24 November 2017	Evora, Portugal	National Gathering of Public and Private Water Management Companies and Authorities
24.	SIVECO, Gov2u	ICT-enabled open government and public sector innovation through digital solutions	24 October 2017	Brussels, Belgium	H2020 E-Government projects - Digital Transformation of Public Administrations. Project Cluster Event on Sustainability and Exploitation of Project Results
25.	SIVECO	SOCIETAL CHALLENGE 5 CLIMATE ACTION, ENVIRONMENT, RESOURCE EFFICIENCY &	8-9 November 2017	Brussels, Belgium	H2020 E-Government projects

		RAW MATERIALS			
26.	SIVECO	Food Security, Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry, Marine, Maritime and Inland Water Research and the Bio economy	15 November 2017	Brussels, Belgium	H2020 E-Government projects - Biodiversity
27.	IP TULCEA	Prefectural Collegium	20 November 2017	Tulcea, Romania	Reunion of public administration authorities, chaired by the Prefect, where important problems of the community are debated/presented.
28.	IP TULCEA	Tulcea County Prefect's Office Annual Report 2017	20 February 2017	Tulcea, Romania	Official presentation of the annual report, in the presence of all central and territorial authorities of the public administration, mass media, NGOs, public.
29.	Gov2u	51st ICA International conference	11 - 14 September, 2017	Tokyo, Japan	The Conference themed Bold Digital Government-dealing with disruptive technologies attended by governmental CIOs local stakeholders and national ministerial representatives

Table 19 : Consortium participation in 3rd party events

4.2.2 Highlights from the FLOOD-serv participation in third party events

The project was presented and promoted in different types of events throughout the 18 months of its implementation.

4.2.2.1 51st ICA international conference

The project was discussed among Breakout Group 4 during Sessions VI and VII on Interaction Day of the [51st ICA International Conference](#) which took place in Tokyo, Japan (11th-14th September 2017). Gov2u partner member, Dora Spyropoulou attended the conference and discussed the possibilities of FLOOD-serv during discussions addressing the topic of

misinformation and dealing with Disaster Management situations. The Conference themed Bold Digital Government-dealing with disruptive technologies was attended by international governmental CIOs from a number of countries from around the world as well as local stakeholders and national ministerial representatives.

Figure 32 : 51st ICA international conference (Tokyo, Japan)

4.2.2.2 25th Scientific Symposium “Deltas and Wetlands”

“Deltas and Wetlands” was the title of the International Symposium that was conducted in Tulcea Romania from the 18th to the 21st of May 2017. Within this conference numerous speakers attended and a variety of subjects around the main theme of the conference were presented. During the final section of the symposium, the FLOOD-serv Partners from IP Tulcea presented the paper: *“Flood Services legislative approach in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management– FLOOD-serv Project”*. This paper presented the main concept of the FLOOD-serv project along with the tools that are created in order to support flood resilience and awareness. According to the abstract: *“The study is documented by parallel descriptions of how the provisions of the European Directives are transposed into the national legislations and it will provide key country characteristics and differences of the governance structure of the flood risk management, which are crucial elements for the effectiveness of the societal risk reduction”*. Additionally, the partners from DDNI presented the study with the title: *“Flood Services needs in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management– Flood Serv Project”* The study examined approach on flood management, from reacting to risk analysis and prevention. Furthermore, it presented: *“the research on the initial needs in the domain of flood risk management and flood related services in the area of Danube Delta and adjacent area. For the past years, Danube Delta National Institute for Research and Development Tulcea (DDNI) has been involved in several flood risk related projects, but the team comes way back with more experience in hydraulic modeling “*.

Figure 33 : 25th Scientific Symposium “Deltas and Wetlands” (Tulcea, Romania)

4.2.2.3 Digital Transformation of Public Administrations Event

The FLOOD-serv project attended the event “[Digital Transformation of Public Administrations Event](#)” that was organized by the Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (*CONNECT*) and the Research Executive Agency (REA). The event was held in Brussels on the 24th October 2017. It brought together 100 persons from a large spectrum of stakeholders, including project representatives, public administration representatives, EU policy makers and professionals active in the investment and start-up community. New opportunities for further expanding our project’s network were explored and new synergies were established. Also valuable information and suggestions around the exploitation activities that EU funded projects in general may follow were collected.

Figure 34 : Digital Transformation of Public Administrations Event (Brussels, Belgium)

4.3 Collaboration with other projects

Synergies (*collaboration*) with EU funded projects that are related with the project’s topic were established. These synergies assisted (*and will continue to assist*) in the communication activities of the FLOOD-serv project in promoting its developments and news also through the networks of these EU projects. In parallel, WP6 leader has undertaken to do the same for these projects (*cross dissemination synergies*). Beyond the communication activities, collaborations have been established in order to exchange knowledge on meteorological risks.

No.	Partner	Collaboration established with	Date	Description of the collaboration activity
1.	CELLENT	SmartGov <u>Contact person:</u> Malgorzata Goraczek	17 – 19 May 2017	Presentation of FLOOD-serv at CEDEM conference in Krems
2.	Municipality of Genova	ANYWHERE <u>Contact organization:</u> Fondazione CIMA , Dir. Civil Protection	5-8 September 2016 During whole	Comparison and coordination between project activities regarding meteorological risk management studied by both projects

			period project	
3.	Municipality of Genova	CLIMAT ADAPTATION PARTNERSHIP	19 January 2017 ON GOING	Contribution about the natural risks management items in order to the candidature for the network coordination
4.	SIVECO	CLARITY <i>Contact person:</i> Thordis Sveinsdottir, Trilateral	November 2016	Assistance in communication activities of the FLOOD-serv project via promoting its developments and news through the networks of CLARITY project.
5.	Gov2u	Mobile Age <i>Contact person:</i> Niall Hayes, Lancaster University	March 2017	Assistance in communication activities of the FLOOD-serv project via promoting its developments and news through the networks of Mobile Age project.

Table 20 : List of established collaborations with other projects

4.4 Direct contact with stakeholders

Consortium partners had face to face meetings and interacted with stakeholders in order to promote the project and also acquire further knowledge on water management risks, meteorological aspects and so on. The activities that were undertaken by partners included:

- presentations in software companies where feedback about the FLOOD-serv platform was received;
- meetings with representatives of universities for possible collaborations and testing the FLOOD-serv platform;
- meetings with representatives of municipalities and ministries for collaboration and testing the FLOOD-serv platform,
- Identification and involvement of stakeholders;
- dissemination and networking the project,
- signing a memorandum of cooperation for free-of-charge hydrometeo advisory.

The full list of activities made as well as their description can be found at the table below.

No.	Partner (s)	Name of contact	Date	Venue/ location of the meeting	Activity description
1.	ANO	Meeting with Civil Protection of Famalicão	17 January 2017	Famalicão, Portugal	Pilot Discussion

2.	Answare	Face to face meeting with the Emergency Coordination Center 112 of the Region of Murcia and its Civil Protection Service	17 November 2016	Civil Protection/112 office in Murcia, Spain	Answare presented its expertise in emergency response (including presentation of Flood-serv project). This meeting allowed Answare to obtain the opportunity to explore new ways of collaboration on projects related to emergency management.
3.	BSK, Exdwarf	Slovak hydrometeorological Institute	11 November 2016	Bratislava, Slovakia	Member of the Advisory board of the project, signed Memorandum on cooperation within the pilot in BSK
4.	BSK	Bratislava Water Company	18 November 2016	Bratislava, Slovakia	Local stakeholder, cooperation within the pilot in BSK
5.	BSK	Slovak Water Enterprise	14 November 2016	Bratislava, Slovakia	Local stakeholder, cooperation within the pilot in BSK
6.	BSK, Exdwarf	Ministry of Interior of Slovakia – Bratislava District office, Department of Environment and Crisis management	30 January 2017	Bratislava, Slovakia	Local stakeholders, cooperation within the pilot in BSK
7.	BSK, Exdwarf	Municipality of Pila and Dolany	1 March 2017	Pila, Dolany, Slovakia	Local stakeholders, cooperation within the pilot in BSK
8.	BSK, Exdwarf	Municipality of Devín	Several meetings from April 2017 – July 2017	Bratislava - Devín	Cooperation within the pilot in BSK

9	BSK, Exdwarf	Municipality of Rača	Several meetings from June 2017 – July 2017	Bratislava - Rača	Cooperation within the pilot in BSK
10.	BSK, Exdwarf	Slovak hydrometeorological Institute	Several meetings from June 2017 – July 2017	Bratislava, Slovakia	Member of the Advisory board of the project, cooperation within the pilot in BSK
11.	CELLENT	Mr. Giorgio Prister <i>(President of MCE)</i>	13 October & 21 October 2016	MCE conference	Discussed the activities of CELLENT during the conference (Info Booth, presentation, etc.)
12.	CMVNF	CMPC - Municipal Civil Protection Commission , meeting	21 November 2016	Vila Nova de Famalicão	Project presentation
13.	CMVNF	Leaders of the municipality, meeting	10 November 2016	Vila Nova de Famalicão	Project presentation
14.	CMVNF	Department of geography of Minho university , meeting	25 October 2016	Guimarães	Project presentation
15.	CMVNF	CDOS - District Commands for Relief Operations, meeting	13 October 2016	Braga	Project presentation
16.	CMVNF	EDP - Entity responsible for the management of the Guilhofrei dam, meeting	14 October 2016	Braga	Project presentation
17.	Exdwarf	Lubica Kolkova, Mayor Bratislava Devin	17 July 2017	Bratislava Devin	Dissemination and cooperation for pilot

18.	Exdwarf	Peter Pilinsky, <i>Mayor Bratislava Raca</i>	13 July 2017	Bratislava Raca	Dissemination and cooperation for pilot
19.	Exdwarf	Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute (SHMU): Type: stakeholder, hydrometeo.advisor SHMU: Vladimir Benko, General Director. Valeria Wendlova, Hydrologist/Advisor.	30 June 2017	SHMU, Bratislava. BSK Bratislava	Signing of memorandum about cooperation, dissemination of project. Outcome: free-of-charge hydrometeo advisory (<i>Mrs.Wendlova is official advisor of FLOOD-serv</i>) and free-of-charge access to SHMU data (<i>weather, water levels etc.</i>). Requirements
20.	Exdwarf	Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute (SHMU): Type: stakeholder, hydrometeo.advisor SHMU: Vladimir Benko, General Director. Valeria Wendlova, Hydrologist/Advisor.	14 June 2017	SHMU, Bratislava. BSK Bratislava	Signing of memorandum about cooperation, dissemination of project. Outcome: free-of-charge hydrometeo advisory (<i>Mrs.Wendlova is official advisor of FLOOD-serv</i>) and free-of-charge access to SHMU data (<i>weather, water levels etc.</i>). Requirements
21.	Exdwarf	Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute (SHMU): Type: stakeholder, hydrometeo.advisor SHMU: Vladimir Benko, General Director. Valeria Wendlova, Hydrologist/Advisor.	02 March 2017	SHMU, Bratislava. BSK Bratislava	Signing of memorandum about cooperation, dissemination of project. Outcome: free-of-charge hydrometeo advisory (<i>Mrs.Wendlova is official advisor of FLOOD-serv</i>) and free-of-charge access to SHMU data (<i>weather, water levels etc.</i>) Requirements

22.	Exdwarf	Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute (SHMU): Type: stakeholder, hydrometeo advisor SHMU: Vladimir Benko, General Director. Valeria Wendlova, Hydrologist/Advisor.	11 November 2016	SHMU, Bratislava. BSK Bratislava	Signing of memorandum about cooperation, dissemination of project. Outcome: free-of-charge hydrometeo advisory (<i>Mrs. Wendlova is official advisor of FLOOD-serv</i>) and free-of-charge access to SHMU data (<i>weather, water levels etc.</i>) Requirements.
23.	Exdwarf	Bratislava Water Company (BVS)	03 May 2017	BVS, Bratislava	Visit of BVS premises, excursion of water management processes and information systems, Dissemination of project and stakeholders network buildup, 2016: Dissemination of project and stakeholders network build-up
24.	Exdwarf	Bratislava Water Company (BVS)	15 November 2016	BVS, Bratislava	Visit of BVS premises, excursion of water management processes and information systems, Dissemination of project and stakeholders network buildup, 2016: Dissemination of project and stakeholders network build-up
25.	Exdwarf	Boris Kovac, Head	14 November 2016	Slovak Water-management Bratislava Enterprise (SVP)	Dissemination, networking for FLOOD-serv project, requirement collection

26.	Exdwarf	Boris Kovac, Head	30 June 2017	Slovak Water-management Bratislava Enterprise (SVP)	Dissemination, networking for FLOOD-serv project, requirement collection
27.	Exdwarf	Jozef Mruskovic, Mayor Dolany	01 March 2017	Municipality Dolany, Slovakia	Dissemination and requirement collection, pilot planning. Interested in pilot especially done testing in Dolany
28.	Exdwarf	RNDr. Radovan Micunek, PhD. <i>Mayor Pila</i>	01 March 2017	Municipality Pila, Slovakia	Dissemination and requirement collection. Not interested in pilot
29.	Exdwarf	Miroslava Gregorova - Head of DoE, Karol Sloboda – Head of DoCM	30 January 2017	Department of Environment (DoE), Bratislava District office. Department of Crisis Management (DoCM)	Dissemination, networking for FLOOD-serv project, requirement collection
30.	GENOVA	A. Morgante – Pres. Municipio Medio Levante	28 February 2017	Municipio Bassa Val Bisagno - GENOVA	Identification and involvement of stakeholders
31.	GENOVA	M. Ferrante – Pres. Municipio Bassa Valbisagno	28 February 2017	Municipio Bassa Val Bisagno - GENOVA	Identification and involvement of stakeholders
32.	GENOVA	University of Genoa – DISPO Department of Social Politics	28 March 2017, 19 April 2017, 10 May 2017	Municipality of Genoa and University of Genoa DISPO	Contribution of the methodology to citizen involvement
33.	GENOVA	University of Genoa DAD – Department of Architecture	28 March 2017, 19 April 2017, 10 May 2017	Municipality of Genoa and University of Genoa – DAD	Identification of the tools to citizen involvement and to receive data.

34.	GENOVA	University of Genoa – DISPO Department of Social Politics	15 June 2017	Municipality of Genoa and University of Genoa	Contribution of the methodology to citizen involvement
35.	GENOVA	University of Genoa – DISPO Department of Social Politics	6 July 2017	Municipality of Genoa and University of Genoa	Contribution of the methodology to citizen involvement
36.	GENOVA	University of Genoa – DAD Department of Architecture	28 July 2017	Municipality of Genoa and University of Genoa	Identification of the tools to citizen involvement and to receive data
37.	IP Tulcea	Petre MARINESCU Tulcea Municipality , Deputy-mayor	13 December 2016	DDNI	Local seminar organized to identify the end users' specifications
38.	IP Tulcea	Paul CONONOV, Water Management System , Director	13 December 2016	DDNI	Local seminar organized to identify the end users' specifications
39.	IP Tulcea	Anastate MORARU, Isaccea Municipality, Mayor	13 December 2016	DDNI	Local seminar organized to identify the end users' specifications
40.	IP Tulcea	Marius IFRIM- Bestepe town hall, Deputy-mayor	13 December 2016	DDNI	Local seminar organized to identify the end users' specifications
41.	GENOVA	CONSORZIO DEI COMUNI TRIDENTINI in collaboration with UNIGE - DAD	21 September 2017	CONSORZIO DEI COMUNI TRIDENTINI TRENTO	Comparison between the ICT tools to involve citizen in the safety and maintenance of the territory
42.	GENOVA	- Dr. Massimo Ferrante (<i>Presidente Municipio Bassa Val Bisagno III</i>) - Dr. Francesco Vesco (<i>Presidente Municipio Medio Levante IV</i>)	11 September 2017	MUNICIPALITY OF GENOA	Planning of the next step of the activities in order to realize the pre-test (mugugn.app) of the Genoa pilot project <i>in collaboration with UNIGE - DAD</i>

		<p>- Prof. F.Balletti (UniGe – DAD)</p> <p>- Dr. Luca Raffini (Unige- DISPO)</p>			
43.	Exdwarf	<p>Tel Aviv Municipality</p> <p>Simona Leibovich, Project Manager – EU Programmes</p>	24 January 2018	Tel Aviv Municipality, Israel	<p>Presentation of Floodserv project, discussed possible collaboration and testing for emergencies (Floods but also other emergencies prevalent in Israel), Solution raised interest (esp. social media, EMC), interest in knowing the user stories and exact possibilities to use the platform. Another call will be scheduled with IT and resilience manager included.</p>
44.	Exdwarf	<p>Tel Aviv University</p> <p>Bruria Adini, PhD and Gili Shenhar, EMBA (Department for emergency and disaster management)</p>	25 January 2018	Tel Aviv University, Department for emergency and disaster management, School of Public Health, Israel	<p>Presentation of Floodserv project, discussed possible collaboration and testing within academia and research projects. During the meeting I gained some valuable insights about used solutions in Israel (buzlla for social media, reporty – app for municipalities). Interested in testing the platform but Herbrev localization would be needed. Another call to be scheduled.</p>
45.	BSK, Exdwarf	Municipality of Devín	Several meetings from August to	Bratislava - Devín	cooperation within the pilot in BSK

			September of 2017		
46.	BSK, Exdwarf	Municipality of Rača	Several meetings from August to September of 2017	Bratislava - Rača	cooperation within the pilot in BSK
47.	BSK	MPS system, s.r.o.	13 December 2017	Bratislava – Office of BSK	Cooperation within the installation of hydrologic measuring stations
48.	Answare	INFO - Development Institute of the Region of Murcia Joaquín Gómez Gómez (<i>Director</i>)	05 December 2017	Answare Office	Flood-serv presentation. With the aim to provide Flood-serv with visibility at regional level, Answare presented the main objectives and achievements of the project to the Director of the INFO, who is the responsible for funding innovative projects in the Region of Murcia.
49.	Answare	Alterna Tecnologías S.L. Francisco Javier Sigüenza Martínez (<i>Director</i>)	18 December 2017	Alterna Tecnologías Office	Flood-serv presentation. Alterna is the company which is now implementing the emergency management software to the 112 Service in Murcia. They provided Answare with some feedback about the EMC and they are interested in the possible exploitation of the EMC.

Table 21 : List of direct contacts with stakeholders (face to face meetings)

The following table presents in detail the items published in media for the period August 2016 – January 2018. This list can be found online at the **FLOOD-serv website** on section “Results”, subsection “[Dissemination](#)”.

No.	Partner	Title of the media item	Media	URL	Date
1.	SIVECO	Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	<i>Agerpres</i>	https://www.agerpres.ro/ots/2016/08/04/inundatiile-consuma-2-1-din-pib-ul-romaniei-16-11-00	4 August 2016
2.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Comunicat e de Presa</i>	http://www.comunicatedepresa.ro/siveco-romania/inundatiile-consuma-2-1-din-pib-ul-romaniei/	4 August 2016
3.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Web PR</i>	http://www.webpro.ro/stiri-it_c-21203094-inundatiile-consuma-2-1-din-pib-romaniei.htm	4 August 2016
4.	SIVECO	Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	<i>AMOS News</i>	http://www.amosnews.ro/inundatiile-consuma-21-din-pib-ul-romaniei-2016-08-04	4 August 2016
5.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>HotNews</i>	http://m.hotnews.ro/stire/21203801	4 August 2016
6.	SIVECO	Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	<i>Ziare pe net</i>	https://www.ziare-pe-net.ro/stiri/inundatiile-consuma-2-1-din-pib-ul-romaniei-4656855.html	4 August 2016
7.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Comunicat e de a faceri</i>	http://www.comunicatedeafaceri.ro/it-c/inundatiile-consuma-21-din-pib-ul-romaniei	4 August 2016
8.	SIVECO	Inundațiile consumă 2,1%	<i>Agora</i>	http://www.agora.ro/stire/inundatiile-	4 August 2016

		din PIB-ul României		consuma-21-din-pib-ul-romaniei	
9.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Live PR</i>	https://www.livepr.ro/inundatiile-consuma-2-1-din-pib-ul-romaniei/	4 August 2016
10.	SIVECO	Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	<i>PR wave</i>	https://www.prwave.ro/inundatiile-consuma-2-1-din-pib-ul-romaniei/	4 August 2016
11.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>STIRI EVENIMENT E</i>	http://www.stirievevimente.ro/stiri/Inundatiile-consuma-2-1--din-PIB-ul-Romaniei-/9316	4 August 2016
12.	SIVECO	FLOOD-serv, proiect european derulat în 7 state: Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	<i>CursDeGuvernare.ro</i>	http://cursdeguvernare.ro/inundatiile-consuma-21-din-pib-ul-romaniei-flood-serv-proiect-european-derulat-in-7-state.html	4 August 2016
13.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Press mania</i>	http://www.pressmania.ro/stiri/societate/stiinta/inundatiile-consuma-2-1-din-pib-ul-romaniei-1757318.html	5 August 2016
14.	SIVECO	Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	<i>M-security NEWS</i>	http://m-securitynews.ro/content/inunda%C8%9Biile-consum%C4%83-21-din-pib-ul-rom%C3%A2niei	5 August 2016
15.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Science HotNews</i>	http://science.hotnews.ro/stiri-tehnologie-21204902-inundatiile-consuma-2-1-din-pib-romaniei.htm?utm_source=feedburner&utm_medium=fee	5 August 2016

				d&u17tm_campaign=Feed%3A+hotnews%2Fyvoq+%28Hotnews.ro%29	
16.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Comunicat e online</i>	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=995003140617978&id=154287148022919	7 August 2016
17.	SIVECO	Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	<i>Curierul de Ramnic</i>	http://ramnic.ro/articole/pnbspspan-stylefont-size-mediumnbspb-styletext-align-justifyspan-stylefont-family-timesromanrinunda-tiile-consuma-21-din-pib-ul-romacircnieispanbspan-stylefont-size-mediumb-styletext-align-justifyspan-stylefont-family-timesromanrbr-spanbspanspanp-80096/2016-08-08	8 August 2016
18	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Cronica de Iasi</i>	http://www.cronica-deiasi.ro/stiri/nationale-externe/Inundatiile-consuma-21-din-PIB-ul-Romaniei-/62816	8 August 2016
19.	SIVECO	Guvernanti atentie – inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei!!	<i>infoBRASOV. net</i>	http://infobrasov.net/guvernanti-atenie-inundatiile-consuma-21-din-pib-ul-romaniei/	9 August 2016
20.	SIVECO	Floods are consuming 2.1% from Romania's GNP	<i>American Chamber of Commerce in Romania</i>	https://www.amcham.ro/index.html/articles?articleID=2703	16 August 2016
21.	SIVECO	(P) Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	<i>SANSA News</i>	http://www.sansanews.ro/stiri/publicitate/buzau/inundatiile-consuma-21-din-	30 August 2016

				piib-ul-romaniei.html	
22.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei Index de Stiri si Articole de Ultima Ora din Romania	<i>008.ro</i>	008.ro	August 2016
23.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>pescurt.ro</i>	pescurt.ro	August 2016
24.	SIVECO	Inundatiile consuma 2,1% din PIB-ul Romaniei	<i>Centrul de presa</i>	centruldepresa.ro	August 2016
25.	SIVECO	Un proiect european de cercetare, coordonat de o companie românească, mobilizează cetățenii din regiuni cu risc de inundații crescut precum Genova, Delta Dunării, Bilbao, Bratislava și Porto	<i>IT Trends</i>	https://ittrends.ro/2016/09/un-proiect-european-de-cercetare-coordonat-de-o-companie-romaneasca-mobilizeaza-cetatenii-din-regiuni-cu-risc-de-inundatii-crescut-precum-genova-delta-dunarii-bilbao-bratislava-si-porto/	1 September 2016
26.	SIVECO	Natural disasters – major concern for European authorities	<i>Nine O'clock.ro</i>	http://www.nineoclock.ro/natural-disasters-major-concern-for-european-authorities/	6 September 2016
27.	BSK	Bratislavský kraj spolupracuje na posilnení	<i>24hod.sk</i>	http://www.24hod.sk/bratislavsky-kraj-spolupracuje-na-posilneni-protipovodnevej-	12 September 2016

		protipovodňovej ochrany		ochrany-cl462172.html	
28.	BSK	Kraj spolupracuje na posilnení protipovodňovej ochrany	<i>MY Pezinok</i>	http://naspezinok.sk/c/20271165/kraj-spolupracuje-na-posilneni-protipovodnovej-ochrany.html	12 September 2016
29.	BSK	Kraj posilňuje protipovodňovú ochranu	<i>PEZINSKO (page 14)</i>	https://issuu.com/regionpress.pezinsko/docs/pk1637?e=5519374/38850113	16 September 2016
30.	Gov2u	FLOOD-serv project: Public FLOOD Emergency and Awareness SERVICE - 1st Newsletter Issue now available!	<i>Joinup platform</i>	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/flood-serv-project-public-flood-emergency-and-awareness-service-1st-newsletter-issue-now-available	14 December 2016
31.	BSK, Exdwarf	Ochrana pred povodňami	<i>Zapadoslovenska televizia</i>	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EWIz59cEbD8&index=2&list=PLmeWD86yY0HlCx4cMVRyaNWAKy8F4XOsJ	20 December 2016
32.	BSK, Exdwarf	Protipovodňová výstraha v Bratislavskom kraji	<i>Radio REGINA</i>	https://reginazapad.rtvsk/clanky/z-regionov/123161/protipovodnova-vystraha-v-bratislavskom-kraji	22 December 2016
33.	IP Tulcea	Local News	<i>Radio Delta Tulcea</i>	n/a	December 2016
34.	Gov2u	Another successful Flood-serv workshop took place in Tulcea, Romania on the 12th and 13th of December	<i>ICA - International Council for IT in Government Administration (Official Facebook page)</i>	https://www.facebook.com/ICA.IT.ORG/posts/1794994990768067	4 January 2017

		2016 at the DDNI.			
35.	Exdwarf	Protipovodňový systém Dunaj neskrotí, včas nás varuje	<i>TV Bratislava</i>	http://www.tvba.sk/home/okolo-dunaja-bude-vystrazny-protipovodnovy-system/	10 January 2017
36.	CMVNF	Famalicao participa em projeto europeu para prevencao do risco de cheias (page 9)	<i>Opinião Pública</i>	http://www.opiniaopublica.pt/pt/opiniaopublica/2017-02-02	2 February 2017
37.	CMVNF	Camara adere a projeto europeu para prevencao do risco de cheias (page 12)	<i>O Povo Famalicense</i>	http://www.opovofamalicense.com/edicoes/860.pdf	7 February 2017
38.	BILBAO	"Flood Service-Meeting" jardunaldiak	<i>Bilbao Newspaper (No.322)</i>	http://www.floodserviceproject.eu/bilbao-newspaper/	February 2017
39.	BSK	Bratislavská župa pripravuje koncepciu ochrany zdrojov povrchovej a podzemnej vody	<i>TERAZ TV</i>	http://tv.teraz.sk/spravodajstvo/koncepcia-ochrany-vodyx5fth9z/11387/	22 March 2017
40.	BSK	Na bratislavskej konferencii sa dnes na Svetový deň vody diskutovalo o jej ochrane	<i>Netky.sk</i>	http://www.netky.sk/clanok/na-bratislavskej-konferencii-sa-dnes-na-svetovy-den-vody-diskutovalo-o-jej-ochrane	22 March 2017
41.	BSK	SVETOVÝ DEŇ VODY	<i>VEGA TV</i>	http://vegatv.sk/index.php?mact=CGBlog,cntnt01,detail,0&c	23 March 2017

				ntnt01articleid=585&cntnt01returnid=50	
42.	Gov2u	FLOOD-serv project: Public FLOOD Emergency and Awareness SERVICE – 2nd Newsletter Issue now available!	<i>Joinup platform</i>	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/news/flood-serv-project-public-flood-emergency-and-awareness-service-%E2%80%93-2nd-newsletter-issue-now-avai	5 April 2017
43.	Gov2u	From reaction to prevention: The power of ICT combined with flood risk management tactics	<i>ICA - International Council for IT in Government Administration (Official Facebook page)</i>	https://www.facebook.com/ICA.IT.ORG/posts/1854514621482770	12 May 2017
44.	GENOVA	flood-serv	<i>Le Vie dell'Acqua</i>	http://www.leviedellacqua.it/2017/05/27/flood-serv-uniniziativa-horizon-2020-che-coinvolge-il-comune-di-genova/flood-serv/	27 May 2017
45.	GENOVA	FLOOD-serv, un'iniziativa Horizon 2020 che coinvolge il Comune di Genova	<i>Le Vie dell'Acqua</i>	http://www.leviedellacqua.it/2017/05/27/flood-serv-uniniziativa-horizon-2020-che-coinvolge-il-comune-di-genova/	27 May 2017
46.	Gov2u	Links To Similar Projects	<i>Mobile Age project</i>	http://www.mobile-age.eu/useful-links/links-to-similar-projects/131-flood-serv.html	27 July 2017
47.	BSK	"Povodne v bratislavskom regióne by	<i>BSV Svet II.Q</i>	http://www.floodserv-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/20	July 2017

		mali být minulostí”		17/07/BVS_Svet_BS K.pdf	
48.	BSK	„Efektívnejší manažment povodňových rizík otestujú Devíne”	“Devincan”	www.devincan.sk	August 2017
49.	BSK	“Úrad aktívne rieši záplavy na Mrázovej ulici”	<i>Website of municipality of Rača</i>	https://www.raca.sk/urad-aktivne-riesi-zaplavy-na-mrazovej-ulici/	21 August 2017
50.	BSK	“Rača dostane viac ochrany pred vodou”	“Račiansky výber” webpage also in print copies	https://www.raca.sk/data/att/4186.pdf	9 September 2017
51.	BSK	“Kraj súčasťou projektu výstražného povodňového systému”	“Senecko” No. 39	https://issuu.com/regionpress.senecko/docs/sc1739	28 September 2017
52.	Bilbao	EXPERTOS ANALIZAN EN BILBAO LA GESTIÓN DEL RIESGO DE INUNDACIONES Y LA ADOPCIÓN DE MEDIDAS PREVENTIVAS INUNDACIONES	20 minutos	https://www.20minutos.es/noticia/3170557/0/expertos-analizan-bilbao-gestion-riesgo-inundaciones-adopcion-medidas-preventivas/	26 October 2017
53.	Bilbao	Una treintena de expertos debaten en Bilbao sobre la gestión de inundaciones	ABC.es	http://agencias.abc.es/agencias/noticia.asp?noticia=2645553	26 October 2017
54.	Bilbao	UNA TREINTENA DE EXPERTOS DEBATEN EN BILBAO SOBRE	ORAIN bizkaia	http://bizkaia.orain.eus/una-treintena-de-expertos-debaten-en-bilbao-sobre-la-gestion-de-inundaciones/	26 October 2017

		LA GESTIÓN DE INUNDACIONES			
55.	Bilbao	Expertos analizan en Bilbao la gestión del riesgo de inundaciones y la adopción de medidas preventivas	GENTE en Bilbao	http://www.gentedigital.es/bilbao/noticia/2255085/expertos-analizan-en-bilbao-la-gestion-del-riesgo-de-inundaciones-y-la-adopcion-de-medidas-preventivas/	26 October 2017
56.	Bilbao	UNA TREINTENA DE EXPERTOS EUROPEOS DEBATIRÁN EN BILBAO SOBRE LOS RIESGOS DE INUNDACIONES DENTRO DEL PROYECTO EUROPEO FLOOD-SERV	Bilbao 24 horas	http://bilbao24horas.com/una-treintena-de-expertos-europeos-debatiran-en-bilbao-sobre-los-riesgos-de-inundaciones-dentro-del-proyecto-europeo-flood-serv/	26 October 2017
57.	Bilbao	Expertos analizan en Bilbao la gestión del riesgo de inundaciones y la adopción de medidas preventivas	Eldiario.es	http://www.eldiario.es/norte/euskadi/Expertos-analizan-Bilbao-inundaciones-preventivas_0_701330125.html	26 October 2017
58.	Bilbao	UNA TREINTENA DE EXPERTOS EUROPEOS DEBATIRÁN EN BILBAO SOBRE LOS RIESGOS DE INUNDACIONES DENTRO DEL PROYECTO	NoticiaPress.es	https://www.noticiapress.es/2017/10/una-treintena-de-expertos-europeos-debatiran-en-bilbao-sobre-los-riesgos-de-inundaciones-dentro-del-proyecto-europeo-flood-serv/	26 October 2017

		EUROPEO FLOOD-SERV			
59.	BSK	“Rozvoj povodňového výstražného servisu”	Webnoviny	https://www.webnoviny.sk/bsk-rozvoj-povodnoveho-vystrazneho-servisu/	27 October 2017
60.	BSK	“Rozvoj povodňového výstražného servisu”	Dobré noviny	https://www.dobrenoviny.sk/c/114639/rozvoj-povodnoveho-vystrazneho-servisu	27 October 2017
61.	GENOVA	ARCHITETTURA LANCIA L’APP “MUGUGN.APP”	IL SECOLOXIX Regional newspaper	http://www.agenziaefficienzaenergetica.it/area-riservata/rassegnastampa-enea/rassegnastampa-archivio/anno-2017/dicembre-2017/Rassegna%20stampa%20del%203_12_2017.pdf	3 December 2017
62.	GENOVA	GENOVA – LA PRIMA FASE DEL PROGETTO SPERIMENTALE FLOOD-SERV	giornalino ORDINE degli INGEGNERI di Genova	n/a	

Table 22 : Media coverage list

4.5.2 Communication activities on partners’ channels

Beyond the items published in third party media referred to FLOOD-serv, the project partners used their organization’s communication channels e.g. partners’ website, press releases, newsletters, other media pages etc. Respective information is included at the table below.

No.	Partner	Article’s Title	Channel	URL
1.	ANO	ANO has embraced a new project	ANO’s Website	http://www.ano.pt/noticias/-/asset_publisher/WbhLLSnWyej3/content/ano-software-desenvolve-aplicacao-para-a-prevencao-de-cheias?redirect=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ano.pt%2Fnoticias%3Fp_i

				d%3D101_INSTANCE_WbhLLSnWyej3%26p_p_lifecycle%3D0%26p_p_state%3Dnormal%26p_p_mode%3Dview%26p_p_col_id%3Dcolumn-1%26p_p_col_count%3D1
2.	ANO	FLOOD-serv advances: Workshop in Portugal	ANO's Website	http://www.ano.pt/en/noticias/-/asset_publisher/WbhLLSnWyej3/content/ano-software-avanca-com-projeto-europeu-para-a-prevencao-do-risco-das-cheias?redirect=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ano.pt%2Fnoticias%3Fp_p_id%3D101_INSTANCE_WbhLLSnWyej3%26p_p_lifecycle%3D0%26p_p_state%3Dnormal%26p_p_mode%3Dview%26p_p_col_id%3Dcolumn-1%26p_p_col_count%3D1
3.	ANO	FLOOD-serv moves forward!	ANO's Website	http://www.ano.pt/noticias/-/asset_publisher/WbhLLSnWyej3/content/projeto-flood-serv-soma-e-segue-a-passos-largos?redirect=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ano.pt%2Fnoticias%3Fp_p_id%3D101_INSTANCE_WbhLLSnWyej3%26p_p_lifecycle%3D0%26p_p_state%3Dnormal%26p_p_mode%3Dview%26p_p_col_id%3Dcolumn-1%26p_p_col_count%3D1
4.	Answare	Flood Serv	Answare's webpage	http://answare-tech.com/en/flood-serv/
5.	Answare	Our team is now presenting our EMC component (Emergency Management Console) in Tulcea @FLOODservEU #FloodAwareness #FloodEmergency	Answare's Twitter	https://twitter.com/answaretech/status/862606209257537540
6.	Answare	Floods are consuming 2.1% from Romania's GNP	Answare's webpage	http://answare-tech.com/en/blog-post/floods-are-consuming-2-1-from-romanias-gnp/
7.	Answare	Our team is now presenting our EMC component (Emergency Management	Answare's Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/answareTech/posts/1980097062223628

		Console) in Tulcea @FLOODservEU #FloodAwareness #FloodEmergency		
8.	Answare	Answare-Tech presentation about our Emergency Management Console (EMC) at the FLOOD-serv Project EU 2nd Consortium Meeting in Tulcea!	Answare's staff LinkedIn profile	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6268711924335153152/
9.	BSK	Kraj posilňuje protipovodňovú ochranu	BSK website	http://www.region-bsk.sk/clanok/kraj-posilnuje-protipovodnovu-ochranu-875880.aspx
10.	BSK	BSK: Konferencia o ochrane vody	BSK website	http://www.region-bsk.sk/clanok/bsk-konferencia-o-ochrane-vody-133597.aspx
11.	CMVNF	Projeto europeu para a prevenção do risco de cheias avança	Webpage of the municipality	http://www.vilanovadefamaliao.org/?it=printnewbreve&co=35008
12.	SIVECO	Inundațiile consumă 2,1% din PIB-ul României	SIVECO website	http://www.siveco.ro/ro/despre-siveco-romania/presa/comunicate-de-presa/flood-serv
13.	CMVNF	Portugal 2020	Webpage of municipality	http://www.cm-vnfamaliao.pt/portugal_2020
14.	Gov2U	FLOOD-serv Project kicks off in Bucharest	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10154571561011057
15.	Gov2U	FLOOD-serv project kicks off in Bucharest!	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/781886404682977280
16.	Gov2U	<u>#FLOODservEU website has been launched!!!</u>	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/783978918994857984
17.	Gov2U	<u>#FLOODservEU website has been launched!!!</u>	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10154589161946057
18.	Gov2U	FLOOD-serv Project Brochure is	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10154675373916057

		available online - designed by Gov2U		
19.	Gov2U	<u>Brochure of FLOOD-serv Project EU available on http://issue.com</u>	Gov2u Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/Gov2u/posts/10154707458046057
20.	Gov2U	<u>Brochure of FLOOD-serv Project EU available on http://issue.com</u>	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/796689878964731904
21.	Gov2U	FLOOD-serv Project Brochure is available online - designed by Gov2U	Gov2u Twitter account	https://twitter.com/Gov2u/status/793067746862833664
22.	GENOVA	Progetto europeo Flood-serv sui rischi naturali: il caso studio di Genova	COMUNE DI GENOVA - WEBSITE	http://www.comune.genova.it/content/progetto-europeo-flood-serv-sui-rischi-naturali-il-caso-studio-di-genova
23.	GENOVA	FLOOD-serv Genova	Social Media Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/groups/flood.serv.genova/
24.	GENOVA	LINUX DAY Genova	Social Media Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/linuxdaygenova/
25.	GENOVA	“Partecipa la progetto europeo Flood-serv con la mugugn.app”	INTRANET server COMGE	https://intranet.comune.genova.it/search/node/flood
26.	GENOVA		University of Genoa WEBSITE	http://geomorfolab.arch.unige.it and news section https://architettura.unige.it/node/422
27.	ANO	Project FLOOD-SERV on target for success!	ANO's Website and Social Media	https://goo.gl/cUU5Dg
28.	BSK	Rozvoj povodňového výstražného servisu	BSK website	http://www.region-bsk.sk/clanok/rozvoj-povodnoveho-vystrazneho-servisu-247474.aspx

29.	BSK	-	BSK Instagram page	https://www.instagram.com/p/BZN7ixUFyL1/
30.	Answare	Our team is today at Bilbao presenting the actual status of our prototypes during the 1st review meeting of the @FLOODservEU project #H2020 https://t.co/eHSPms08s5	Answare Facebook Page	https://www.facebook.com/answareTech/posts/2059305027636164?pnref=story
31.	Answare	Our team is today at Bilbao presenting the actual status of our prototypes during the 1st review meeting of the @FLOODservEU project #H2020 https://t.co/eHSPms08s5	Answare Twitter account	https://twitter.com/answaretech/status/923894983178031104/photo/1?utm_source=fb&utm_medium=fb&utm_campaign=answaretech&utm_content=923894983178031104

Table 23 : Communication activities on partners' channels

4.6 Publications

No.	Partner	Title of publication	Date	Authors	Status
1.	DDNI, IP Tulcea	Flood Services needs in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management– Flood Serv Project	18-21 May 2017, Tulcea – Romania	Nichersu Iuliana, Petroschi Daniela, Nichersu Iulian, Bănescu Alexandru	Presented in the 25th International Scientific Event “Deltas and Wetlands” 2017
2.	IP Tulcea, DDNI	Flood Services legislative approach in the context of Danube Delta area flood risk management– Flood Serv Project	18-21 May 2017, Tulcea – Romania	Petroschi Daniela, Nichersu Iuliana, Nichersu Iulian	Presented in the 25th International Scientific Event “Deltas and Wetlands” 2017

Table 24 : Publications List

5 Performance Measurement and Evaluation

The current chapter measures the performance of each communication and dissemination tool used as well as the communication activities made. In the context of evaluating the effectiveness of the activities performed the KPIs (*Key performance indicators*) as set in D6.2 are also provided. Nevertheless, the KPIs are referred to per year measurement and the whole duration of the project. For avoiding confusion and providing accurate information to the reader, we present all measurements made in M12 and in M18. The final evaluation of all activities will be made in deliverable D6.6 Final Communication Report.

5.1 Website Performance & KPIs

The measurement of website's performance was made via AWstats.

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>KPIs</i>	<i>Achieved number</i>
Pages per month in M12 (<i>on average</i>)	≥ 400	12,081
Pages per month in M18 (<i>on average</i>)	n/a	11,122
Visits per month in M12 (<i>on average</i>)	≥ 80	1,301
Visits per month in M18 (<i>on average</i>)	n/a	1,479

Table 25 : Website performance & KPIs

5.2 Social Media Performance & KPIs

Facebook Page	KPIs	Achieved number
Total Page Likes in M12	≥100	71
Total Page Likes in M18	n/a	118
Total Page Likes growth per year	≥65%	
Posts per month (<i>average of M12</i>)	≥4	4.2
Posts per month (<i>average of M18</i>)	n/a	3.4

Table 26 : Facebook Page performance

Twitter Account	KPIs	Achieved number
Followers in M12	≥100	42
Followers in M18	n/a	50
Followers growth per year	≥65%	
Tweet impressions per month (<i>average of M12</i>)	≥300	600

Tweet impressions per month (average of M18)	n/a	496
Profile visits per month (average of M12)	≥30	20.5
Profile visits per month (average of M18)	n/a	15.4
Tweets per month (average of M12)	≥4	3
Tweets per month (average of M18)	n/a	3

Table 27 : Twitter Account performance

LinkedIn Account	KPIs	Achieved number
Connections in M12	≥100	107
Connections in M18	n/a	131
Connections growth per year	≥65%	
Posts per month (average of M12)	≥4	3.5
Posts per month (average of M18)	n/a	2.4

Table 28 : LinkedIn Account performance

Google+ Account	KPIs	Achieved number
Followers in M12	≥10	4
Followers in M18	n/a	5
Followers growth per year	≥50%	
Posts per month (average of M12)	≥4	2.3
Posts per month (average of M18)	n/a	1.8

Table 29 : Google+ Account performance

5.3 Newsletter Performance & KPIs

Information around the newsletter subscribers will be derived from the backend of the project's website.

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>KPIs</i>	<i>Achieved number</i>
Subscribers to e- Newsletter in M12	≥60	22
Subscribers to e-Newsletter in M18	n/a	25
Subscribers growth per year	≥65%	

Table 30 : Newsletter's indicators measurement

5.4 Digital Publishing Platforms Performance & KPIs

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>KPIs</i>	<i>Achieved number</i>
Number of documents related to the project published per year on Scribd, Slideshare and Issuu	≥5	35 (11 on Scribd, 18 on Slideshare, 16 on Issuu) in M18
Number of views (<i>on average</i>) per document on each digital publishing platform	≥15	19.6

Table 31 : Digital Publishing Platforms indicators measurement

5.5 YouTube Performance & KPIs

<i>Measured Indicators</i>	<i>KPIs</i>	<i>Achieved number</i>
Number of videos published per year	3	No video published
Number of views (<i>on average</i>) per video	≥100	-

Table 32 : You tube performance & KPIs

5.6 Overview of WP6 activities (M1-M18)

This section provides an overview of the activities made during the reporting period. Many of the KPIs set in D6.2 have as time frame the whole duration of the project. Thus, we present briefly in the table below the numbers achieved so far. In deliverable "D6.6 Final Communication and Dissemination Report" a further analysis will be made.

<i>Type of Tool or Activity</i>	<i>Measurement Unit</i>	<i>Number</i>
FLOOD-serv Website	Unique visitors	19,076
	Visits	26,622

	Pages	200,203
	Articles uploaded at Project news	20
Social Media	Facebook Page likes	118
	Twitter followers	50
	LinkedIn connections	131
	Google+ connections	5
Digital Publishing Platforms	Items uploaded at Scribd	11
	Items uploaded at Slideshare	18
	Items uploaded at Issuu	16
Newsletter	Newsletter Issues published	3
	Newsletter subscribers <i>(voluntarily subscription via the project's website)</i>	25
Press releases	Press releases published	8
Promotional materials	Types of promotional materials created	4 <i>(flyer, factsheet, poster & brochure)</i>
	Types of promotional materials translated	2 <i>(flyer, poster)</i>
	Languages translated	5 <i>(Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Slovak, Romanian)</i>
Outreach activities	Events organized by the FLOOD-serv consortium	19
Third party events <i>(public events)</i>	Participated & presented the project in third party events	29
Media coverage	References in press & media <i>(third party)</i>	62

	Number of interviews/news broadcasted at radio and/or TV	5
	Links/articles/references in FLOOD-serv partners' institutional websites, newsletters, social media accounts	31
Collaboration with other projects	Total number of formal and informal collaborations with other projects	5 (<i>in total</i>)
	Established collaborations in dissemination synergies (<i>cross-links</i>) with other EU funded projects	2
Publications	Number of publications	2

Table 33 : Overview of WP6 activities

5.7 Evaluation

After providing to the reader all the available information around the performance of tools and channels employed and activities made within the reporting period on communication activities few aspects need to be addressed.

The KPIs set in the deliverable D6.2 have as time frame measurements either per year or throughout project's duration. Taking into consideration that this report covers the period until the month 18, comments can be made for the achieved numbers in M12. Moreover, KPIs that have as a time frame the whole duration of the project will be commented in the deliverable D6.6 Final Communication and Dissemination Report. For the time being we can only measure the so far performance of these actions.

Thus, according the presented information in previous sections, the achieved numbers in project's website compared to the KPIs can be characterized as successful. Concerning the social media accounts, FLOOD-serv LinkedIn account met the goal of 100 connections in Y1 (*i.e. 107 connections in Y1*) while in Facebook, Twitter and Google+ failed. Also, the number of posts (*average*) for each account was not met in M12 with only exception the Facebook page with an average of posts slightly over the KPI of 4 posts per month.

The newsletter subscribers were low (*22 subscribers*) for Y1 and the target of 60 subscribers at the end of the first year was not achieved and in M18 the number were still low (*25 subscribers*). The performance of the FLOOD-serv profiles in digital publishing platforms was successful.

Overall, the communication and dissemination activities such as media coverage, number of interviews in TV and radio, references in press, events organized by the consortium participation in 3rd party events have already reached and exceeded the set KPIs that were referred to the whole duration of the project.

6 Update of the Dissemination Plan

Taking into consideration that the submission month of this deliverable is M19 (*February 2018*), according to the plan presented in D6.2, the communication activities soon enter the final phase as depicted in **Figure 36**. The communication activities of the project during its lifecycle have been divided into the following three phases:

- **First Phase** - Communication for Awareness (*August 2016 - January 2017*)
- **Second Phase** - Communication for Action (*February 2017 - March 2018*)
- **Final Phase** - Communication of Final Results (*April 2018 - July 2019*)

Figure 36 : Phases of Communication Activities

The final phase involves the promotion of the final results, motivate further participation of stakeholders in the project events, and promote exchange of experiences and knowledge sharing with related initiatives and take-up of the project results. It will include the following communication actions:

- **Press releases** for announcing: **a)** in each pilot country the implementation of the national pilots, **b)** demonstrate the FLOOD-serv Integrated System, and **c)** announce the final results of the project;
- **Newsletter issues:** will be published in M20, M24, M28, M32 and M36;
- **Video creation** for presenting D4.6 Integrated system;
- Design and creation of the **final project brochure** that will describing the final results of the project;
- Upload at project's website on section "Deliverables" all **public FLOOD-serv deliverables**;
- Upload at project's website on section "Publications" the papers and research work of the project;
- Submission of **Research Briefs** to similar projects, scientific and academic communities;
- Expand the network and collaboration with other **EU funded projects**;
- Present the FLOOD-serv in **public events**;
- Organize events for engaging potential end-users and attract more visibility around the project and its results;
- Submission of **non-scientific articles** to EU magazines;
- Articles submission to scientific journals.

7 Conclusions

This document constitutes a report of the communication and dissemination activities made by the FLOOD-serv consortium within the period August 2016 – January 2018 (*M1-M18*). The communication tools and channels are also outlined. The actions described within this report were planned in deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 which respectively submitted in October 2016 (*M3*) and November 2016 (*M4*).

Evaluating all the activities performed corrective actions should be taken in few channels and tools employed because they were not as successful as expected when the key performance indicators were set in the Dissemination plan. However, most of the communication activities of the consortium attracted a lot of attention from a wide range of audience either in local (*national*) or international level. In terms of KPIs these activities have already reached and exceeded the set ones in time frame referred to the whole duration of the project.

Summarizing, during the reporting period we have used a mixture of tools and activities in order to achieve the objectives of this work package and be prepared for the next period i.e. *M19-M36*. The actions undertaken will also be made in respect of exploiting the results of the project after the end of EC funding.

The current deliverable was submitted in February 2018 (*M19*) as foreseen in the DoW.

APPENDIX I – Target Audiences

End-users

No.	Group	Description
i	<p>End-users of the flood risk management proactive and personalized citizen-centric public service application</p>	<p>Individuals and institutions/organizations from the pilot sites (<i>Danube Delta - Romania, Genova- Italy, Bilbao - Spain, Bratislava Self-Governing Region - Slovakia, Ave Valley Region - Portugal</i>).</p> <p>The project plans to establish a Community of Interest consisting of existing communities of people from the pilot sites and engage with them to shape the direction in which the FLOOD-serv platform will be developed, tested and evaluated.</p> <p>They will be empowered by the project to share their ideas, knowledge, skills, and experiences in order to explore new methods and tools that can enhance their own disaster resilience and that of their communities.</p> <p>The Community of Interest will allow the Consortium to identify real, actual needs in the potential user pool and take them into consideration; to adapt the platforms to meeting these needs and to respond to feedback.</p> <p>The project will provide opportunities for community members to take leadership roles and this can motivate many members of the community to get involved in the process of flood risk mitigation and response.</p> <p>The following persons and institutions/organizations from the pilot sites will be targeted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Grassroots groups and organizations interested in the management and conservation actions regarding water and land b. Land owners and administrators of properties c. Members of NGOs that are service providers (<i>e.g. shelter</i>) and volunteers' organisations of civil protection d. Informal citizens networks (<i>offline and online</i>) that are engaged in social issues e. Trade organizations which are representatives of interest groups (<i>e.g. forestry and agriculture, tourism, hunting, fishery, etc.</i>) f. Persons that experienced a flood in the past or were affected with material losses due to a flood in the pilot sites

		<p>g. University students who are tech-savvy and engaged in social issues</p> <p>h. School teachers</p> <p>i. Water users associations</p> <p>j. Emergency planners and services</p> <p>k. River basin authorities</p> <p>l. Public authorities dealing with emergency services</p> <p>m. Individuals with expertise in physical science and engineering, geographical science, social and behavioral science, economics, and public health with professional experience from research, public policy, emergency and disaster management</p> <p>n. Computer programmers and others involved in software development (<i>technology enthusiasts, early adopters, geeks, IT professionals from companies, SMEs and ICT start-ups</i>)</p> <p>o. The wider general public,</p> <p>i.e. communities/neighborhoods including the resident population as well as local businesses (<i>companies from the sectors concerned with water supply and purification, dredging, maritime activities, fishing activities, expert ecological consulting services, waste water treatment, irrigation, hydro power, mining, agriculture, tourism promotion, leisure activities, transport, architecture and construction etc.</i>) who could be affected by the flood risk management issues and impacted by measures.</p>
<p>ii.</p>	<p>Research community</p>	<p>Digital social innovation organisation and networks, researchers in areas such as flood risk management, participatory open government, open data integration, human sensing, content harvesting, distributed knowledge co-creation, decision support systems, collective intelligence, data mining etc. as well as international organisations involved in flooding issues (<i>e.g. IAHR- The International Association of Hydraulic Engineering and Research, IAHS-the International Association of Hydrological Sciences, EGS- the European Geophysical Society etc.</i>).</p> <p>They could be interested to feed the project results and know-how into further RTD projects related to ICT-enabled government, collective intelligence, PSI re-use, open data, etc.</p>
<p>iii.</p>	<p>Academic Community</p>	<p>European schools and training institutes focused on teaching and training on a variety of topics related to flood</p>

		<p>management, social science and technology, public affairs & administration.</p> <p>The know-how acquired in the context of the project could be exploited by the academic community for educational purposes with the main aim of defining and offering to students innovative topics for theses and projects, new courses contents, developing products such as books or manuals from research and lessons learned during the project.</p>
iv.	Business and industry	<p>including both ICT solution providers and consulting industry with interest in Public sector innovation</p> <p>They can develop commercial ICT applications based on research and technological innovations created by the project and consult governments and other public service organizations on how to harness the technology developed by the project to transform their businesses.</p>

Table 34 : End users

Decision Makers / Replication Actors

Decision makers and practitioners of national civil protection authorities across Europe, National/Regional Hydrological Services, emergency planners and services, civil protection experts, municipal departments/government agencies in charge of water and sewage, electricity provision, broadband provision, municipal heating, spatial planning and construction, transportation, environment and health, IT/GIS.

They may be interested in the project results from the application side (*customers*) for adoption and/or extending this system to other policy areas related to sustainability (*e.g. management of other types of disasters, community policing, early warning etc.*), to different sites in the pilot countries and to different countries, at the same level as the pilot system and at lower and higher scales.

Stakeholders

No.	Group	Description
i.	EU level, national and local non-governmental Organisations (NGOs)	<p>representatives of public bodies (<i>EUPAN – The European Public Administration Network</i>), of European Regions (AER - the Assembly of European Regions, EU-level and national NGOs and their networks active in the disaster reduction and emergency management field, open government data advocates and access to information advocates (<i>e.g. Open Knowledge Foundation, Access Info Europe, EDRI-European Digital Rights, Communia- the international association on the digital public domain etc.</i>).</p> <p>They can use the results of the project for advocacy activities aimed at institutional reforms at local level related to crisis management and emergency response process (e.g. adoption by the governments of platforms for</p>

		<p>collective awareness that can be used for feeding data contributed by distributed human and environmental sources for improved early warning system and for more participatory democratic processes for problem solving) They can also use the results of the project for influencing policies at national and EU level aimed at stimulating the creation and delivery of new public services utilising new web technologies, coupled with open public data. Some of them may have connections and collaborations with the local groups of interest for this project, thus helping us to reach them or to disseminate the project results among them.</p>
<p>ii.</p>	<p>Multi-stakeholder group of partners across various disciplines for innovation</p>	<p>(e.g. research, industry, finance, NGO, ICT, etc.), as well as the demand and supply sides of innovation- The Steering Group, Task Force and Action Groups under the European Innovation Partnership on Water, European Innovation Partnership on Smart Cities and Communities, European projects in the area of digital social innovation, other projects funded under the INSO-1-2014/2015 (ICT-enabled open government) topic - <i>CLARITY, DIGIWHIST, Euth, Mobile-Age, OpenBudgets.eu, OpenGovIntelligence, RECAP, ROUTE-TO-PA, SIMPATICO, smarticipate, smarticipate, STEP, WeGovNow, WeLive and YourDataStories</i> - as well as other international projects and organizations of relevance for the FLOOD-serv project.</p> <p>They can integrate knowledge coming from our project. The FLOOD-serv Consortium can investigate collaboration opportunities and exploiting synergies with these groups and projects.</p>
<p>iii.</p>	<p>Science advisory bodies / Expert groups</p>	<p>Horizon 2020 expert advisory group on Societal Challenge 6, Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative and reflective societies, the High Level Group of Scientific Advisors of the EC Scientific Advice Mechanism, The EU’s Open Innovation Strategy and Policy Group etc..</p> <p>The project findings may be of interest for them when provide opinions, reports and recommendations for action at EU and at national level to foster the ICT-enabled public sector innovation</p>
<p>iv.</p>	<p>DRM Knowledge Centre</p>	<p>Within the European Flood Awareness System it provides a Forum of Information Exchange to have a harmonized approach to Disaster Monitoring.</p> <p>The results of FLOOD-serv are related to flood disasters monitoring, therefore are of interest to the DRM Knowledge Centre.</p>

<p>v.</p>	<p>European and international Standardization bodies</p>	<p>(E.g. ISO, CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Coordination Group ‘Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities’ SSCC-CG, OGC-Open Geodata Consortium etc.)</p> <p>Standardization bodies have enormous influence within the European Union as they produce and recommend technical and legal standards to address the needs of affected adopters of new technologies.</p> <p>BS 11200:2014 Crisis management, and ISO 22320:2011 Societal security – Emergency management – Requirements for incident response are two standards offer guidance and good practice to help organisations plan, establish, operate, maintain and improve their crisis management capability. Compliance with these standards is crucial for ensuring interoperability and for this reason they will be followed by the partners in issuing the project requirements as much as possible. FLOOD-serv may contribute to the standardization process if specific extensions and refinements are required, by making recommendations in this regard to the standardization bodies.</p>
<p>vi.</p>	<p>Media from pilot sites as well as national, European and international media.</p>	<p>Media institutions are not only stakeholders in the project but also the means to raise awareness about the project. Therefore media serve both as a goal and as a means.</p>

Table 35 : Stakeholders

Policy Makers

Policy makers in both legislative and executive bodies at local, national, regional and EU level (*MEPs, MPs, ministers, mayors*) from across Europe that holds the responsibility for the coordination and implementation of eGovernment services and for disaster risk management. They can use the project knowledge and results to drive better policies by embedding the results into policies and practices at local, regional, national and EU levels related to flood event management policy domain (*e.g. stimulating public participation and collective actions*) and to ICT enabled open government.

Funding Authority – European Commission

The FLOOD-serv Consortium has an informative dialogue with the Project Officer representing the Commission. The Project officer will be informed about interesting topics, news and events concerning the project. EC could also support the dissemination of the project. In this regard, news and success stories related to the project can be submitted for publications and websites managed by the European Commission.

General Public from EU countries

The EU citizens will be informed about the European added value of activities supported by Horizon 2020 programme and how the aims and outcomes of FLOOD-serv are relevant to the people’s own disaster resilience and that of their communities.

APPENDIX II – Promotional Materials

The current appendix includes screenshots of the promotional materials of the FLOOD-serv project.

Flood Awareness Better Served!

FLOOD-serv
FLOOD Emergency and Awareness SERVICE

FLOOD-serv (Public FLOOD Emergency and Awareness SERVICE), is a project that aims to provide a complete solution for flood awareness, response actions as well as education regarding flood risks. Through the use of different mobile technologies, the project will make information available in a transparent manner in order to increase the openness of ICT-based technology platforms in the public sector.

An Emergency Management Console will gather all available information from social media, visualize emergency status through geomapping and track actions to be executed.

A pro-active and personalized citizen-centric public service tool to empower local community involvement in the design of flood relief actions.

[FLOOD-serv Project - @FLOODservEU](#) [@FLOODservEU](#)
[FLOOD-serv Project EU](#) [FLOOD-serv Project EU](#)

Consortium

SIVICO, cellent, NEWARE, Go2U, Bilbao, ANO, EXDWARF, FAMILIÇÃO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693599

Figure 37 : FLOOD-serv Flyer (EN)

FLOOD-serv
Public FLOOD Emergency and Awareness SERVICECall

FLOOD-serv is a pro-active and personalised citizen-centric public service application that will enhance citizens' involvement and use the collaborative power of ICT networks to:

- Empower local communities to actively participate in the design of emergency flood relief actions.
- Provide ICT-enabled solutions assisting public administration to raise civic awareness on flood risks, effects and impact and to enable collective risk mitigation solutions and response actions.
- Encourage the development and implementation of long-term, cost-effective and environmentally sound flood relief actions through collaborative power engaging government, private sector, NGOs and other civil society organizations as well as citizens.

Expected Impact:

- Stimulate the creation, delivery and use of new services on a variety of devices, utilizing new web technologies, coupled with open public data;
- Offer more personalized public services that better correspond to the needs of users with the goals of creating a common dialogue, reducing losses, and decreasing vulnerability to flood disasters;
- Reduce the administrative burden of citizens and businesses (e.g. collecting information from citizens only once) by introducing a web-based personalised public service as a solution dedicated to flood risk management that will digitize the transactions between public administrations and users;
- Increase transparency and trust in public administrations by gathering the information from the citizen and making it available to the public and the public authorities in order to take specific actions for the wellbeing of the citizens.

Specific Objectives:

- To make use of the best available data in order to identify the location and potential impacts that natural hazards as floods can have on people, property and natural environment;
- To improve the systems of warning and emergency communications;
- To provide support for the public authorities and government institutions' hazard relief efforts, including planning and action coordination;
- To inform the public on the risk exposure to natural hazards and how they can prepare, respond, recover and mitigate the impacts of such events.

[FLOOD-serv Project - @FLOODservEU](#) [FLOOD-serv Project EU](#) [@FLOODservEU](#) [FLOOD-serv Project EU](#)
 Questions? Contact us: info@floodserv-project.eu

Consortium

SIVICO, cellent, NEWARE, Go2U, Bilbao, ANO, EXDWARF, FAMILIÇÃO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693599

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Figure 38 : FLOOD-serv Factsheet (EN)

APPENDIX III – AWstats Glossary

The following table presents in detail the explanation of each term used for measuring the performance of the FLOOD-serv website. The information presented are extracted by the following link: https://awstats.sourceforge.io/docs/awstats_glossary.html

Term	Explanation
Unique Visitor	<p>A unique visitor is a person or computer (host) that has made at least 1 hit on 1 page of your web site during the current period shown by the report. If this user makes several visits during this period, it is counted only once. Visitors are tracked by IP address, so if multiple users are accessing your site from the same IP (such as a home or office network), they will be counted as a single unique visitor.</p> <p>The period shown by AWStats reports is by default the current month. However if you use AWStats as a CGI you can click on the "year" link to have a report for all the year. In such a report, period is a full year, so Unique Visitors are number of hosts that have made at least 1 hit on 1 page of your web site during the year.</p>
Visits	<p>Number of visits made by all visitors. Think "session" here, say a unique IP accesses a page, and then requests three other pages within an hour. All of the "pages" are included in the visit, therefore you should expect multiple pages per visit and multiple visits per unique visitor (<i>assuming that some of the unique IPs are logged with more than an hour between requests</i>)</p>
Pages	<p>The number of "pages" viewed by visitors. Pages are usually HTML, PHP or ASP files, not images or other files requested as a result of loading a "Page" (like js,css... files). Files listed in the NotPageList config parameter (and match an entry of OnlyFiles config parameter if used) are not counted as "Pages".</p>
Hits	<p>Any files requested from the server (<i>including files that are "Pages"</i>) except those that match the SkipFiles config parameter.</p>
Bandwidth	<p>Total number of bytes for pages, images and files downloaded by web browsing.</p> <p>Note 1: Of course, this number includes only traffic for web only (<i>or mail only, or ftp only depending on value of LogType</i>).</p> <p>Note 2: This number does not include technical header data size used inside the HTTP or HTTPS protocol or by protocols at a lower level (TCP, IP...).</p> <p>Because of two previous notes, this number is often lower than bandwidth reported by your provider (<i>your provider counts in most cases bandwidth at a lower level and includes all IP and UDP traffic</i>).</p>

Table 36 : AWstats Glossary